

MARKET RISKS MANAGEMENT INSTRUMENTS FOR AGRICULTURAL MARKETS AND EU POLICY

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Abstract: *Most economists congregate on the idea that commodity price instability should be reduced. Since at least one century a variety of instruments have been designed to that end, without much success, especially for agricultural commodities. The failure might be a consequence of the fact that most policies have neglected the reason for price fluctuations. The latter's are endogenous, caused by the market equilibrium local dynamic instability, which means that any measure relying on the "law of large numbers" is likely to be inoperative. In addition, because, in agriculture, the production function is homogenous and of degree one, any effective stabilisation leads to over production. Only production quotas can cope with these difficulties. They may be designed in such a "way as to maintain the essential feature of market equilibrium, i.e. marginal cost equating price.*

Keywords: equilibrium point, exogenous/endogenous fluctuations, insurance (price) storage /retrival, limited quantities, marginal cost, market operators,. market volatility, production techniques, risk of producers, volatility/fluctuations in agricultural prices

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Agricultural price volatility is not new a phenomenon. For instance, figure 1 below displays the wheat producer price in France from 1701 to 2013. It seems even more volatile in the early 18th century than nowadays.

Figure 1 Wheat producer price in France, 1701- 2014²
Prices expressed as number of non qualified working hours per ton

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² Fourastié (1966) is the main source for this diagram. From 1701 until 1950, this author compiled wheat prices in current currency on as many markets records as possible. Then, he computed the

But much earlier sources, such as the Bible and Joseph's story in the genesis book, mention a virtually infinite volatility in Egypt during the 18th century BC³

Now, such a situation is never "good" for anybody. Of course, farmers benefit from high prices. But in such situations, their gains are smaller than the losses for the consumer. Conversely, consumer gains from low prices do not offset producer losses. After a few rounds up and down, everybody is worse off, as demonstrated in any first year course of economics... In effect, the marginal cost equating demand is socially "optimal" in some sense. With a volatile price, this equality never holds, meaning volatility is always "bad" for any market. Now, agricultural prices are exceptionally volatile, as illustrated on figure 2: while car prices fluctuates modestly (and decrease in the long run), retail tomatoes prices vary from one to four in a few weeks (and are stationary, if not increasing). The same sort of diagram could have been obtained with many couples of agricultural and non agricultural commodities. Then, the question arises of how to prevent (and cure) price volatility?

Figure 2 Retail prices of tomatoes and cars in large American cities, 193-2011
Seasonally adjusted indexes base 100: 1984-86. Source: Economagic

quantity of wheat a non qualified worker could buy at the time with one working hour. The price of the working hour itself derives from the compilation of parochial archives, which indicate the cost and working time for the renovation of church seats. Eventually, the series was augmented using the legal minimum wage rate as the labour price, and the INSEE's price of wheat.

³ Joseph predicts a famine, and urges the King to set up a granary. In effect, the first year of dearth, people from the Middle East come to the granary to buy grain. The second year, the famine is still lasting, but all the available money has been spent. "And when money came to an end in the land of Egypt and in the land of Canaan, all the Egyptians came to Joseph, saying, give us bread! for why should we die before thee? For our money is all gone...". And Joseph, in a way, creates money by taking a mortgage over the regional herd... In other words, without the Joseph's genial invention of the mortgage, the food price in Egypt at that time would have virtually reached infinity!...

No scientist can escape the idea that, in order to answer this question, one should try to understand the deep reasons which, beyond appearances, explain such a situation. It is clear that, if prices are volatile in the case of agricultural (and a few other) commodities and not elsewhere, then, there should exist some specificities explaining this phenomenon. In what follows, we shall present the hypotheses which have been under discussion in this respect, and the associated remedies.

Possible causes of agricultural prices volatility

On this subject, there exist a large consensus on what can be called the “primary causes”, as well as deep dissensions regarding the “secondary causes” – although the later are essential from a practical point of view.

The primary cause of agricultural prices volatility is tied with the famous “King’s law”, that is, the low elasticity of food demand with respect to price. In effect, small changes in the quantities supplied on markets engender large price variations, because consumers (like the Egyptians in the Bible) are ready to leave their whole wealth when their survival is threatened, while they would not increase their food consumption by the smallest bit even if price fall near zero. As a consequence, a fall of 1% in the supply of almost any agricultural good will rise the corresponding price by far more than 1% - perhaps 5 or 10% - while an oversupply will trigger a price decrease of the same order of magnitude. All economists congregate on such an explanation of the large volatility of agricultural and food prices. But this explanation is not sufficient, since, at this stage, one does not see why supply is changing, even if changes are modest. Here is the core of the disputes between economists regarding this question. Some of them invoke “exogenous causes”– weather, plant and animal diseases, etc... - while others argue on the possibility of “endogenous causes”, tied with the intimate functioning of markets. We shall now discuss these two approaches.

Exogenous fluctuations

Nobody can deny the fact that a farmer’s harvest depends on weather or on sanitary hazards. But are such events likely to affect supply on markets?

The answer is certainly positive whence only small local markets are at stake. This is because if my own harvest is bad, there are all the chances that my neighbour’s harvest of is bad too. Thus, climatic conditions are likely to result in variable supply (hence large price fluctuations) on a small market, collecting goods over a narrow region. Yet, the reasoning cannot be extended beyond very particular cases and for large markets.

Figure 3 Correlation between barley yields in European small regions according to distance and differences in mean yields (source: Tarasov, 2011; Boussard & Tarasov, 2013)

Mean yields in small regions (Ukrainian oblast, French department, German lander, etc..) are observed, and a linear tendency determined. Differences in production techniques) and distances between regions are determined. Correlations are computed between the residuals of tendencies in each regions. Each point corresponds to one correlation according to distance and yield difference. The surface is built upon the least quadratic difference between points

First, even at the local level, meteorological hazards might not affect all farmers at the same time: a hail storm can devastate my field, and leave my neighbour's untouched! But above all, the correlation between yields in two different locations is decreasing with the corresponding distance, as shown on figure 3. It shows that the correlation between yields hazards in two European regions becomes negligible as soon as the corresponding distance encompasses 500 to 1000 km. In this way, as soon as a market basin is larger than about 1000x1000 km, the "law of large number" holds, and the supply on such a market should remain independent of exogenous shocks. This result is not surprising. For instance, Cobble *et al.* (2007) shows that yield variation coefficients are relatively small when measured at the federal US level, even if they are large in general when measured at the county level. An this reasoning has been a strong argument in support of agricultural liberalisation (e.g. Bale & Lutz, 1974)

And this is easily understandable. For what concern meteorological events, contrary to a common creed, they rarely affect large areas uniformly. Indeed, on a

map, they look like “leopard skins”, with multiple “good” spots in the middle of large unfavourable perturbations, and *vice versa*.

Figure 4 illustrates this point. It shows the variations of the NDVI index⁴ over northern America during the corresponding weeks (week 32, beginning of August) of two noticeable years: 2011, often considered as a severe drought, and 2014, a very “normal” year. Indeed, one does not see very large differences between these two maps, even if the locations of green and red spots are not the same.

Figure 4 - NDVI over north America during week 22 of two different years
Situation 2011 (outstanding drought) *Situation 2014 (first normal year after several droughts)*

Regarding the consequences pests and diseases, the chances that they affect large areas simultaneously are not nil. Yet, they are small, and sanitary precautions are most of the time successful.

Thus, price fluctuations could have been explained by exogenous accidents a long time ago, when transportations were difficult and lengthy. Nowadays, in a matter of hours, a few trucks could suffice to carry over food in large enough quantities to feed the whole population of a large city. In such a context, the explanation of price fluctuations by exogenous events seems short.

A contrario, even if all conditions are met for climatic factors to be at the origin of fluctuations, they often do not explain *all* observed price changes. In his study of the price of Florida’s orange juice, Roll (1984) provides a striking example in this respect. The orange tree Florida orchard extends itself over a relatively small area, about 100 x 100 km around Jacksonville. The whole production is sold on a specific market, which can be considered as well isolated from other sources of

⁴ The NDVI ((‘Normalised Difference Vegetation Index’) is related to the health of the vegetation in a point. In fact, it measures the way the vegetation reflects solar light, which depends upon how much are plants turgescence. Here, “red” zones represent areas where drying plants are dominant, while “green” zones correspond to places where plants are normally watered.

orange juice. Orange trees are extremely sensitive to frost, a relatively rare accident in Florida, but which occurs from time to time. In case of frost, the whole orchard is devastated, and the harvest in jeopardy. Roll was interested in the price of the orange juice futures contracts – contracts passed in January for a delivery in July. In January, it is easy to predict a rise in July price if a frost occurred in December. In this context, expecting a relation between the climate and the price of futures orange juice contracts passed in January seems reasonable. In effect, Roll demonstrates the existence of a statistically significant relation of this type. Yet, this relation is far from explaining the bulk of the variability of the futures prices of the Florida orange juice... Other mechanisms are thus at work, and are to be identified...

All the above developments lead to the conclusion that one should envisage other sources of agricultural price variability than exogenous events. This is what we shall do now, with the endogenous theory of price variability.

Endogenous fluctuations

Endogenous prices changes have nothing to do with external factors. They are engendered by the dynamics of the market itself. The starting point of the reasoning is the “cobweb model” as made famous by Ezekiel (1938)⁵.

The central idea of this model is the existence of a lag between the decision to produce and the delivery on markets. Because of this lag, production decisions are not based upon any observed price, but upon an *expectation* – the price guessed by the producer at decision time. Ezekiel assumes this expectation is simply the current price during the previous period. Then, assuming that, for some reason, the quantity supplied at time 0 was q_0 , the observed price at time 1 is p_1 – a high price on figure 5. At that price, producers are bound to deliver q_1 the next time. But q_1 is too large, and the price falls at p_2 ... At price p_2 , the supply is q_3 , and so on...

Such a process can result in three types of outcome: If the ratio “slope of the demand curve over slope of the supply curve” is less than one in absolute value, then the difference between each price and quantity from one period to the following one is decreasing in absolute value: the system “converge” toward equilibrium (this is the situation pictured on figure 5). If the ratio is greater than one, this difference is increasing as time passes: the system “diverges”. Finally, in the special case of the ratio being unity, the system is “periodic”, the same prices and quantities coming back each two periods.

⁵ Despite the legend, Ezekiel (he was one of the President Roosevelt advisor for agriculture during the 1930 crisis) is not the author of the model, which apparently had been developed by Kaldor (1934) as a follow up of works by Timbergen on the dynamics of maritime freight.

Figure 5 - The cobweb diagram

Of course, the two last situations cannot be observed in the real world: a periodic motion is not observable because, after a few rounds, producers would have noticed the high profitability of counter-cyclical production, which would lead them to take opportunity of it. By so doing, they would destroy the above mechanism, which would have therefore disappeared. Also, the “diverging” situation is not possible to last any more, because, after a few periods, it implies negative prices and quantities which are not feasible.

Thus, the cobweb model is not realistic. Yet, it delivers one main message that any economist should keep in mind: with an inelastic demand – this is the case of agricultural products – a market equilibrium point is *unstable*, like a ball at the top of a pencil, while it is stable in the opposite situation, like a ball at the bottom of a cup. Consequently, in the case of “luxury products” – those for which the demand is elastic – market solutions lead to the optimal point where marginal cost equates price, and the price stays there. On the contrary, in the case of first necessity products, those with a rigid demand, the chances of converging toward the optimal equilibrium position are lean.

Now, the problem is to know what happens to markets when the demand is inelastic. Clearly, the original cobweb, with linear supply and demand curves, does not bring much information on this point. Ezekiel himself was perfectly aware of that. He suggested to solve the problem by assuming S shaped supply and demand curves, but this is not very convincing, because one does not see why should these curves be S (or any other letter!)- shaped. We need more subtle and deeper explanations of the fact that markets are still functioning even if they permanently stay away from equilibrium, and what are the consequences of this situation.

Obviously, the market does not “explode” (with prices and quantities going toward plus and minus infinity) because something forces it to come back toward the optimal equilibrium as soon as it is sufficiently far away of it, just as a ball which

would be attached at the top of a pencil by an elastic string. But what, here, plays the role of the elastic string ? Many hypothesis have been envisaged to answer this question. Two of them seem valuable, one linked with risk, the other with financial considerations.

Figure 6 - A sample result of the « risky cobweb»

Marginal cost: $P=0.35 Q + 2$; Demand function: $P= -3.5 Q + 10$;

Risk aversion $=0.05$; Expected mean price: 6 ; Starting point : $Q=1,5$

Let's first consider risk. Market operators know that prices are volatile. Even more, they are aware of production and demand conditions. Therefore, they can very well detect any "anomalous" condition, implying a risk of "shifting regime". Thus, even without expecting any immediate change in the mean price, they can associate an increased risk with a situation really too far away of equilibrium. Now, risk is an important determinant of production decisions. Actually, producers never equate marginal cost with demand price, but with its *certainty equivalent*⁶. As a consequence, since the certainty equivalent of a price is always less than its mean, the quantity produced in an uncertain environment is smaller than it would be under "price certainty", and the mean price higher. This illustrates the perverse effect of risk, and the inefficiency of volatile prices. It may also help understanding why are prices prevented to reach infinity: as they become more volatile, production decreases, and mean price increases. But this increase in mean price is an incentive to increase production... at the end, the complex interaction between these two contradictory forces pulls back the system in the direction of the equilibrium whence it stays far from it, just like the elastic string does for the ball at the top of the pencil...

⁶ The certainty equivalent of a price is defined as the certain price which would lead to the same decision as do an uncertain one. For instance, nobody would pay 50 \$ to have the right to be given 100 \$ subject to one toss with probability 0.5. Yet, many would accept such a risk if the stake is 1\$ instead of 50 \$. In the between, there exists a number x – say, 40 or 30 \$ - for which a given decision maker is *indifferent* between playing or not playing. Then, it can be said that, for this decision maker, the certainty equivalent of the 0.5 probability of a 100\$ gain is precisely x . It is to be noticed that x is a personal (and transitory) characteristic of each decision maker...

Figure 6 shows a sample result from a fairly simple “risky cobweb” model built on this basis (Boussard, 1976). Expectations are constant, (here, 6.0.). Risk for period t is measured by the square of the difference between this expectation and the price at time $t-1$. The linear equations of the demand and supply (=marginal cost) curves are as indicated. Such a graph is not really similar with a true agricultural price series, like those of figure 1 and 2, at least because it is perfectly “stationary” instead of “trendy”. Yet, it displays some of the characteristics of a random price, although it is not random at all, and perfectly deterministic. In fact, it is a “chaotic” series, in the sense of the word in mathematics: the solution of a differential equation which does not converge, nor diverges, nor is periodic. Not only the precise values of the terms of the series, but even its general shape are “sensitive to initial condition”, as shown by figure 7, obtained with the same model and the same parameters except the starting point of the series (1.51 instead of 1.50): of course, the two curves of figure 6 and 7 are completely different, despite very similar parameters!

Figure 7 - Another result of the same model as for figure 6

All data identical with those of figure 6 except the starting point: $q = 1.51$ instead of 1.50

It means that predicting prices on the basis of past series is impossible, except in the very short run. Indeed, this model helps understanding the futility of such an exercise. Finally, the succession of large fluctuations and of relatively steady spells must be noticed.

The risk is not the only way to generate chaotic market motions. Financial considerations could interfere with the above mechanism, and might add a few complications to the system. In effect, even if farmers expect high prices, they cannot increase their production rapidly. Even with credit, they have to accumulate a certain quantity of own money before envisaging investments and production growth. Conversely, after being indebted, if they do not stop completely in bankruptcy, they must continue to produce at whatever price. Again, the corresponding constraints are likely to change the time path of the adaptation of production to market signals, and to lead to a chaotic motion of price throughout time, in place of the simplicity of the original cobweb.

Thus, be it a consequence of the farmers' behaviour in face of risk, or of financial constraints, or both, this line of explanation of endogenous fluctuations leads to consider agricultural price series as chaotic. A rather unpleasant consequence of this situation is that any intervention in the system will modify its parameters, and, consequently, result in unpredictable consequences. Here is the main difference between the endogenous and the exogenous fluctuations. The latter are amenable to interventions which will not alter the source of the disorder, but only cure its consequences. In the case of endogenous fluctuations, the problem of intervention is that it has to tackle the engendering mechanism at its very source. Otherwise, any intervention will change the parameters of the series (for instance, the frequency of low prices), thus jeopardizing all the benefit /cost computations made beforehand.

The reality of agricultural price fluctuations

Thus, two sorts of mechanisms, exogenous and endogenous, might engender price fluctuations on agricultural markets. The former seems at work on isolated markets, such as in Africa, where supply comes from relatively small regions, within which all producers are submitted to the same natural hazards. The latter, on the contrary, stand as the sole possible explanation of price fluctuations in large international markets supplied from many remote locations. In such an environment, the "law of large number" holds, and precludes ascribing the origin of fluctuation to climatic or similar hazards.

In fact, it is possible to argue that both mechanisms jointly play a role in the two situations, although perhaps with a different intensity in each location and institutional setting. This is not a good new, because the remedies to be envisaged in order to avoid these detrimental phenomena are different in each case, and probably contradictory one with each others.....

We shall now discuss these contradictions in the light of the agricultural policies within the European Community. First, we shall examine the case of the policies designed to cope with exogenous fluctuations. Then, we shall see that such policies are very likely to fail, and lead to disasters in the context of endogenous fluctuations. And we shall end with considerations on how to replace them...

Consequences for EC policies: the case of exogenous fluctuations

In the case of exogenous random fluctuations, two main types of methods are available in order to mitigate the detrimental effects of prices changes: insurances and storage.

Insurances: extent and limits

Insurances are built upon the "Law of large numbers" (LLN). The LLN specifies the properties of the sum of a set of random variables, each of them "small" by comparison with the sum. If these variables are "independent" – or nearly so -, and if the number of variable is "large" enough, then the variability of the sum is

very small, at the point of being negligible. Of course, this statement is extremely imprecise, because one should have defined the terms “small”, “independent”, “large”, “variability” etc... Indeed, several “laws of large numbers” do exist, differing by the precise meaning attributed to these words. Yet, the above formulation is sufficient to grasp the essence of the theorem, and to understand its usefulness, as well as its limits, when making use of it in the insurance business.

In effect, because of the LLN, an insurance company can promise its customers to pay them a sum of money subject to the occurrence of some random event, in exchange of a fixed non random premium, and that, without taking itself the smallest risk, provided that the above mentioned requirements are fulfilled: the probability of each random event must be independent of the others, the promised sums must be small by comparison with the total, etc.. If these conditions are satisfied, the sum which will be disbursed each year by the company can be predicted with great precision, in such a way that the premiums can easily be fixed at a rate which will cover all expenses tied with payment triggering events, augmented of the management costs and a reasonable benefit. The only real risk taken by the company would be to miscalculate the probabilities of damages... At the same time, the consequence of the system is a redistribution of the money collect through premiums: it flows from the “lucky” (who pay premiums without immediate benefits) to the “unlucky” (who’s indemnities are much larger than the premiums). For that reason, insurance companies are often called “mutual”.

Of course, the above mentioned conditions definitely exclude any “price insurance”: if price are low, they are low for everybody. It is therefore impossible to pay the damages suffered by the “unlucky” with the premiums collected from the “lucky”. In technical terms, we would say that the “price risk” is almost perfectly correlated between each subscriber, thus precluding any recourse to the LLN. The only possibility which would be open in this respect would rely on the independence of one year with respect to the others. But in this case (and assuming years are independent one from each other, which is still to be demonstrated), the problem would be essentially financial, since inter-annual transfers of money would be necessary. Above all, the financial equilibrium would require a “large number “ of years – in practice, something like 500 or 1000: the planning horizon of insurance companies is not so far!. And, of course, this infeasibility of the “price insurance” implies a similar infeasibility of any “revenue insurance”, since a revenue insurance contract would be the product of a yield insurance and of a price insurance contract...

By contrast, a yield insurance contract is theoretically feasible, although under conditions. Such a contract would guaranty a payment to a farmer whom harvest would have been less than normal for reasons out of his or her control. Such a risk is “small”, at least if the number of such contracts held by the same company is “large” – say more than 1000- 10000. Yet, if all these contracts are localised within the same geographical region, individual risks are highly correlated: it means that to be

credible, a company will need to operate over continental sized areas. Notice that the European area is large enough for that, which could be a reason (among others!) for the European Union.

But the main problem for yield insurance is with the above proviso "out of his or her control". In effect, without adequate specifications in the contract, nothing prevent the subscriber to neglect all necessary cares, and discover at the end a very poor yield, justifying an indemnity... For this reason, yield insurance contracts must be carefully written⁷, specifying the techniques which have to be employed on the insured crop, and the mean to check they have been actually put in operation. An alternative is to specify some sort of easily verifiable event triggering the payment (for instance, a hail storm). In this case, the payment is not really linked with the actual yield deficit, but with the occurrence of the specified event, whatever its actual consequences on the own yield of a particular beneficiary.

There is still another obstacle to yield insurance development: the damage reducing techniques. For instance, it is possible to develop irrigation systems to avoid the risk of drought, or use pesticides to prevent undesirable diseases. Such techniques are costly in general, but whether the corresponding cost supersedes the cost of insurance remains a question specific to each situation. Often, the benefit is larger with the risk prevention technique, which reduces the attractiveness of the crop insurance contract.

Now, for the collectivity point of view, there is an additional benefit of using prevention techniques rather than insurance: Even if a crop insurance system can wipe out the damages caused to the farmer, it does not suppress their consequences for the consumer. The latter is still affected by the deficit in overall harvest, and the corresponding price increase. Such a consideration should especially be taken in account when designing an agricultural policy involving crop insurance subsidisation: the later is only a second best, which helps farmers, but not consumers. Even more, if one recalls the above considerations regarding the "mutual character" of insurance schemes, and the fact that insurances only shift the burden of damages between subscribers, then a subsidy to crop insurance is nothing else than a disguised price subsidy, which should be considered as such by the WTO⁸.

From this last point of view, crop insurance is far from being a very efficient mean of coping with the instability of agricultural prices. Yet, by (to some extent) preserving farmers from bankruptcy, it can reduce the long run effects of a temporary accident which, otherwise, could have weakened the producing system for a while. Also, by avoiding farmers being submitted to exceedingly large business risks, it can

⁷ The Spanish crop insurance scheme stands as an outstanding example in this respect.

⁸ For some reasons – perhaps because the diplomats in charge of drafting the Marrakech treatise were not very acquainted with insurance economics - it is not the case, which constitutes a logical breach in the WTO agreements.

induce them to increase production, to the consumer benefit: these are not negligible benefits. But, as we have seen, this instrument cannot be employed everywhere any time.

Storage

Storage is an alternative to insurance in natural hazards remediation. Indeed, it is historically the first one to have been put in operation as a food security policy, as shown for instance by the Bible, which mentions it in Egypt about 1800 years BC. In effect, and contrary to insurance, since it is designed to avoid famines, it is directed toward consumer's rather than producer's benefit.

The mechanism at work is simple and well known: one buys commodities when harvests are good. At that time, prices are low, and this action tends to increase them, for the producer benefit. Commodities are stocked for a while, until another harvest is bad and prices high. Then, the stock is sold, which depresses the high price, for the consumer benefit. But the selling price is still higher than the buying price, in such a way that the storage operator has also a benefit. Because of this circumstance, there does not exist any reason for public authorities to be involved in such operations: the stockpiling mechanism can work within a perfectly liberal setting.

In addition, if the shocks are really of exogenous origin, with stationary probabilities, there exist efficient algorithms which minimize the risk of being out of stock, or of saturating the storage capacity⁹.

Thus, storage results in a multitude of miraculous effects, benefiting to producer, consumer and storage operator, as well as stabilizing prices. They do not need any subsidy, as soon as the storage operator can keep the difference between purchasing and reselling prices. In presence of so many obvious advantages, it is surprising that it does not seem to expand itself spontaneously at its optimal level... Yet, experience shows that, most of time throughout history, in view of the inability of private operators to do the job, storage has been operated by public entities, be it the Egyptian Pharaohs, the *anonnes* of the Roman empire, the "lords" of feudality (and their castles as granaries), etc.... Worse, there exist many examples of private storage operators being called "speculators" and severely chastised (if not simply killed!) for being responsible of famines.

In fact, this is not so surprising. Often, operators are misled. Instead of "buying low and selling high", they (unwillingly) do just the contrary: because they are afraid prices could still increase, they buy "high", thus increasing price again, self fulfilling expectations, and creating penury. Or they make the same mistake in the opposite direction when prices are low.... These observations might lead to the conclusion that there exists a flaw in the above reasoning about the ability of storage to solve the volatility problem within a pure liberal framework....Actually, this flaw is not difficult to find: it lies in the assumption according to which we are in presence of

⁹ In this respect, the pioneer work is by Gustafson (1958). A basic reference is William & Wright (1991). A recent contribution is Gouel & Jean (2011).

purely exogenous fluctuations, with perfectly defined probabilities, while expectation errors are tied with endogenous mechanisms.

Thus, the price stabilisation methods based on the “exogenous source of fluctuations” assumption are in jeopardy if applied in a different context of endogenous fluctuations. This is especially clear in the case of storage: the slope and location of the supply and demand curves are modified by the existence of storage in such a way that the probabilities of gluts or penuries are not constant anymore. This is the reason for why any operator, even in possession of the most improved Gustafson’s algorithms, will be mistaken at the end, and deserving people’s anger against speculators.

In such a context, we have now to turn our attention to price stabilisation within an endogenous fluctuation framework.

Consequences for EC policies: the case of endogenous fluctuations

As noticed above, whatever the cause of fluctuations, once the necessity to lower their amplitude is recognized, an economist is naturally tempted to find some sort of innovation capable of getting the desired result within a purely liberal framework, without public policies interventions. The “futures markets” seem to be able to bring such a solution. We shall first discuss the possibilities in this direction. Yet, their potential is probably smaller than expected. Thus, we shall have to envisage various methods for policy interventions.

Are futures markets sufficient to avoid the detrimental consequences of price variability?

On a futures market, operators exchange promises: for instance, the first of October, operator “A” promise to deliver x tons of wheat (with a specified quality) at location y , next 1st August, and operator “B” promise to buy it at that time for a specified price. There exist variants of this kind of promises: for instance, “A” can promise to deliver only if price is greater than z (or smaller than z'). This later kind of arrangement is an “option”. Yet, the typical transaction is the first one, upon which we shall focus our attention, the others adding unnecessary complexity in the analysis.

The main advantage of such a possibility is that the seller (here “A”) is perfectly sure of the price it will get at delivery time. In this way, “A” can organize production and decide investments on the basis of known prices. In such a setting, there are all the reasons for that marginal cost equates price, thus guarantying market optimality.

Yet, at delivery time, there are no reasons for that the “spot price” (the current price at that time) be the same as the “promised” price. This implies two consequences: first, the actual selling producer price is not the marginal cost anymore. Second, there are always one winner and one loser in each transaction.

A first consequence of this second remark is that the loser is tempted not to fulfil engagements... In view of this difficulty, futures markets operate under the

supervision of an authority which calls losses and pays gains day after day, adjusting the (small) daily changes of prices all the time between promise and delivery. If one day, one of the participants does not comply with the adjustment, it is at once evicted out of the market and cannot operate any more... In this way, everybody is sure that transactions will be correctly ended at due time, whoever the loser.

But the fact that any promise is sure to be fulfilled does not suppress the loser's frustration. The later can feel to have been a fool to let embarked in such a disaster... hence, the main drawback of price volatility does not disappear with the existence of futures markets. The decision to sell or buy through these institutions is always risky, with the detrimental consequences of such a situation. In addition, the time between promise and delivery is usually short – six months to two years – which is often not long enough to cover the risk of agricultural investments, and facilitate credit opening to farmers. Most newly established young farmers would like to know how they will be (and at which price they will sell!) in 10 to 20 years from now...

Finally, futures markets are open to “speculators”, that is, persons who promise to buy or sell, without the least intent to do it (because they “do not touch commodity”!), but because they hope to resell the contract to another operator with benefit before its term. In this way, they operate exactly like the above described storage operator. The only difference lies in the fact that the stock is now “virtual” instead of being “real”. Therefore, those analysts who think in terms of exogenous risks are right to credit them with the faculty of lowering price volatility, just like the “real” storage operators. And just for the same reasons, these futures markets speculators, when their expectations are wrong, probably increase volatility, and ruin themselves at the same time¹⁰...

Thus, while futures markets may bring some help in face of exogenous shocks, there are no reasons for that they can stabilize anything in an endogenous fluctuation context. And since no other “liberal” solutions seem to qualify for that, we have to turn our attention toward the possibility and pitfalls of public intervention.

Public fixed price for unlimited quantities

If the very cause of price vagary lies in the market itself, then a solution to avoid it would be to sever all ties between agriculture and market... Historically, such is the conclusion reached by Henry Wallace and Rexford Tugwell, the agricultural advisors of the US President Roosevelt during the 1930's. Consequently, the Roosevelt administration began buying any supplied quantity of

¹⁰ Notice that not all speculators ruin themselves. Some of them keep their profits. The mechanisms at work here might be instrumental in creating and maintaining wealth inequality.

specified commodity at fixed price. Then, goods were stored or resold on the market under administrative supervision.

We shall not here tell all the many events which accompanied the implementation of this decision¹¹. At the end, after world war II, it was adopted (with variants of secondary importance) not only in the US, but also in almost all non socialist countries. It ended with outstanding successes: not only was the US capable of feeding post-war western Europe in 1945-50, but also, and above all, it avoided the world famine that many analysts of the 1950's forecasted for the years 1990-2000.

The reason is easy to understand: new techniques – machines, fertilizers, pesticides – were put in operation at that time. Such innovations requested large quantities of capital. With volatile prices, in the previous period, the corresponding investments had been impossible to finance. But with stable prices, lending without excessive risks was made possible for banks. Yet, the system was not sustainable, as we shall see.

In effect, figure 8 shows the problem: be it in France or in the USA (the same kind of graph could have been obtained with data from many other countries), yields, under such a regime, are rapidly growing, up to the point of encompassing all solvable needs. This is visible on these graphs, with the “kink” on the precise dates at which guaranteed price policies begun, either in the US or in France. Similarly, in the recent years, one see a conspicuous slowing down of the yields increase in France. There is at least a serious suspicion that it is linked with the abandonment of fixed prices policies in this country, even if some analysts ascribe it to global warming (but why should global warming stop yields increase?).

Figure 8 - Wheat yields in France and USA, 1815-2015

¹¹ The AAA (Agricultural Adjustment Act) was rejected by the Supreme Court because it was in some sense “socialist”. It was issued again under “ecologist” considerations (to prevent the erosion of Middel West soils by the “dust bowl”...). Many other side events occurred.

Figure 9 - Supply and demand with unlimited price guarantee

There is another approach (a little bit more abstract) to the same problem: If the agricultural production function is “homogenous and of degree one”, then the marginal cost must be constant, meaning the supply curve is parallel to the “x” axis (figure 9). With a price guaranteed for any supplied quantity, the demand curve is also parallel to the same axis. Two parallel lines cross over at infinity... A price guaranteed policy for unlimited quantities unavoidably leads to an infinite production...

Here is the reason for which these policies were successful in avoiding famines. But at the same time, they necessarily lead to over production after a while. For years, the main producing countries avoided the problem by storing excess production at a huge cost¹². Subsidizing exports was also a common practice, which raised diplomatic problems, because beneficiaries argued that, by selling quantities at dumping prices, developed countries prevented their own farmers to sell their products¹³. But such expedients have their limits. Alternative solutions had to be found.

In the eyes of a standard economist, the most natural of them was to lower guaranteed price, in order to decrease incentive to increase production beyond limits. Such solutions had been envisaged in the EC during the 1980's. Yet, figure 9 make evident the associated difficulty: nothing change if price is lowered by a small amount, and remains greater than the production cost, while production falls to zero if the price change is large enough to reach a value under the later. None of these two

¹² In the EC, it had been envisaged to store excess quantities of butter in the ice of the Groenland, a solution which at least, would have avoided the cost refrigeration...

¹³ An argument which is both true and false. It is true that, under free trade, subsidised imports make difficult for local producers to reach their “natural” local market. But they are not the only obstacle in this respect: lack of infrastructures and other characteristics of underdevelopment play also a role here. A tax on subsidized developed countries exports would have allowed developing countries to get governmental revenue for building infrastructures, while maintaining a minimal level of supply to urban consumers that the missing public investment would have prevented to get from local sources in the absence of such resources.

situations is satisfying. This is the rationale for “production quotas”, and the reason of their institution in the EC during 1980’s, especially for milk¹⁴.

Guaranteed price for limited quantities

“Production quotas” consist in an arrangement by which public authorities promise producers to buy a given quantity (the “quota”) at a given price. It looks like a futures market contract (cf Boussard, 2002), except that the buyer is the government. Normally, all the quotas rights of the producers of one country sum up at a level close to the corresponding internal consumption. In that way, because farmers are interested producing at least this quantity, food security is guaranteed in the country operating such a policy. Here is the true utility of this system, and the reason to implement it.

Yet, there exist several variants in this implementation. The most important ones concern what to do if farmers produce beyond their allocated quotas.: In the case of sugar beets in Europe, producers could produce more than their quotas, provided the quantity in excess be sold at the international price and for export only. In the case of milk, producing more than quota brought penalties. We shall not discuss here the details of the system, but rather its principle.

It raises several problems. The first one is how to attribute the quotas between producers. Under a strict liberal philosophy, they should have been auctioned, in such a way that those with the larger comparative advantage could buy the more production rights. Yet, in Europe, such auctions have never been organized, and quotas were allocated on the basis of “historical references”: a given farmer was entitled to produce x% of his recorded production during the two or three years preceding the institution of quotas. In cases of succession, retirement, sales, etc., determining the exact extent of production rights was somewhat a headache. In practice, quotas were attached to land, which is far from being a satisfactory solution.

Another problem arises because, under such a regime, production structures are more or less “frozen”. It is not necessarily a bad thing: for instance, there are reasons to think that, without quotas, milk production would have deserted mountainous regions, because milk collection is more difficult in this setting and thus more costly. Since tourists like watching cows on mountains, that would have been a tragedy for tourism. But in general, all the restrictions to the production system evolution do not make easier seeking low production costs. Organizing quotas exchange markets might be a way of escaping this difficulty. Such institutions have rarely been officially created, although in practice, it is generally possible to buy or sell quota rights on a side unofficial market.

¹⁴ Notice that production quotas had been a very old idea for sugar, recognized in the 1947 “Havana chart”, and actually implemented at producer levels in most European countries after this date. .

Finally, there is the over quota production problem. Even with a carefully managed farm, and plans not to encompass limits, there is a possibility that an “exceptional harvest” is larger than the quota. In addition, some farmers may be tempted to produce beyond their quotas.

The first case rarely raise any problem: it is usually possible to find a colleague in deficit who accepted to take the extra production on its account. The second is more difficult. We have seen that the international treaties on sugar permit over-quota production at the encompasser’s risk. Similar arrangements had been envisaged for milk in Canada (Mercier Gouin, 2004). They were rejected by the WTO Dispute Settlement Body, on the ground that, by subsidising the production under quota, the government facilitates investments, and thus, indirectly subsidises whole production. Although it is true that the existence of quotas makes investment easier, such reasoning is somewhat surprising, because it could be transposed to many other situations such as subsidized insurances...

Thus, production quotas policies are far from being free of difficulties. Yet, they guaranty a minimal supply for the domestic consumer, as well as survival for producer. These are not small advantages. The above difficulties can be solved. The main objection lies in the fact that support prices under quota might be unnecessarily large.

Indeed, there have been documented cases of obvious exaggerations. Then farmers extort undue advantages over other citizens, as described in the famous article by Gardner (Gardner, 1992). But this is precisely one of the advantage of quotas to bring a natural solution to this difficulty: the magnitude of the undue rent is easily known by the observation of the price of quotas on the (official or unofficial) market were quotas rights are exchanged, as noticed above.

In effect, in the long run, with a constant return to scale production function, and constant output price, production costs adjust themselves to price through changes in the price of fixed factors. Consequently, the price of production rights is the difference between the “genuine” production cost – the cost of all other production factors – and the current price. Too large such difference means that the output price is unnecessarily high, and could be reduced without jeopardizing production. At the same time, this price should not be null, since the quota constraint must be binding. Otherwise, the corresponding policy would not be effective. It is surprising that this method of guaranteed prices management seems generally neglected by policy makers...

Thus, in the whole, a quota system might be the most efficient way of coping with agricultural price variability, or, at least, the less inefficient. Yet, as we have seen, it may be implemented through a variety of specifications, each with their own advantages and drawbacks.

Conclusions

1. The negative consequences of agricultural price fluctuation are so detrimental that public intervention must be envisaged whenever natural market forces do not solve the problem by themselves. This is true even if such action can contradict the pure liberal *doxa*. Of course, it is out of question to let us deprived of the benefits of the comparative advantages, nor to keep afloat inefficient producers. But the message transmitted by prices must be meaningful, instead of delivering a difficult to interpret noise.

2. We do not have any undisputable solution for that, the more as proposed remedies are deeply different, depending upon the “exogenous” or “endogenous” character of the mechanisms and events which generate instability. Actually, both sources of instability are simultaneously at work, whence remedies which work in one of these situations are almost contradictory with those for the other.

3. This is a case for increased research. We badly need additional works in agricultural economics on this subject of price volatility. Above all, they should be free of dogmatism, be it “liberal” or “interventionist”, just analysing the mechanisms at work, and deriving recommendations from the observation of facts, in the line of the experimental method.

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INTEGRONIC INTERFERENCES IN THE ROMANIAN BIOECONOMY, WITH APPLICATIONS AT THE FOOD ACT PATTERN

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Abstract: *The paper approaches the model reorientation concerning the alimentary pattern on bioeconomic principles and in the integronic dynamics of the model components. It is analyzed the interference of the agri-forest pasture systems with the agri-zoo-food systems as a harmonization of integronic type in the models of the environment-economy complex systems. As an aim, there is pursued the change of economic paradigm through a networking with the environment resources, linked to the food safety for the decades to come. The paper objectives are linked to the identification of components of the alimentary complex system, referring to agri-food, industrial food and complex food from gastronomy, as well as their interferences through multiple integrations in relation to the impact upon the consuming population. There are described applications referring to the understanding of advanced integration of complex food (dishes) and hyper-complex ones (menus) and of the operational techniques specific to gastronomic engineering.*

Keywords: bioeconomy, food act, gastronomy, integronics.

INTRODUCTION

Starting from one of the most worrying scripts, namely: water and food crisis in the decades to come will be much more serious and devastating than the present economic-financial crisis, to apply bioeconomy principles to the whole food act becomes a viable solution. The essence of the future (under peace conditions) is in fact: food and water of very good quality. That is why food security, sustainable agriculture and bioeconomy need an ever better integration in order to contribute to the human food harmonization.

Agriculture, forestry, fishing and aquaculture, together with industries based on „bio concept”, are integrative part of the food act and, of course, of the European society economy. Based on the utilization of limited natural resources, these sectors also produce process biologic resources in order to satisfy the consumers ‘demand and a large scale of industries for food products, animal food, bio-energy and basic bio products.

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But unfortunately, in many parts of the worlds, it is observed that, regarded as a whole, we register an ever hungrier planet. Subnutrition is particularly severe, especially for children, as it may make them grow up slower and makes them vulnerable to disease. Until the year 2050, we will be approximately 9 billion people on the planet, which means that we will need 70 % more food for equilibrated nourishment. In antithesis, in developed countries, the permanent access to food with a high content of fats and carbohydrates, together with change in life style, makes obesity to become a real problem, as well as other illnesses of the „civilization” [Puelles M., 2004, Gruia R., 2013].

BIOECONOMY is the profound change of world’s economic paradigm. To introduce natural environment in relation to demographic evolution in the equation becomes obligatory. But the big practical problem is that, on this basis, there is a harsh fight for what we call strategic resources, i.e. water and food, but also green energy. That is why development shouldn’t be made by resource consumption, but, at levels and rhythms that allow their regeneration, by a sustainable development.

Under this context, one must be aware of the place and role of Romania in the globalised bi economy. Thus, we mention that Romania’s gold is not the mineral one, buried under the mountain, but the thin layer of fertile soil, to which water is added and our country’s exceptional geomorphological conditions. Romanian bioeconomy has all chances to develop extremely well because it still possesses important possibilities to use these resources. „*Romania’s huge capital is given by natural resources*”: out of Terra’s 9 bio-geographical regions, Romania detains 5, having the most important eco-region at global level. More than half of the Carpathians, the wildest nature, are in our country. More than half of Europe’s big carnivorous is to be found in Romania. Then we have the Danube Delta, the wet zones and virgin forests etc.

We are speaking of a true treasure, much richer than the one Russia has lost, for example, namely the **pure genetic basis** that our country has, being among the very few countries in Europe detaining all these things. If we mention only the 220.000 ha of virgin forest, then the chocolate chernozem, the most productive of all soil types, to be especially found in Dobrogea, one can see the certain capacity to sustainably develop the country. You cannot have durable development without the fundament given by pure natural resources. Romania enrolls in the zone of big traders, being a genetic multiplicative potential for countries that only have financial resources, but not natural ones too (or “have forest, but not woods”).

Besides all these, solid knowledge is necessary, in order to successfully negotiate Romanian bioeconomy in severe world competition. In order to consciously negotiate the advantages that food and quality water give you in a world with ever bigger alimentary problems.

Under this context, the objective of the paper becomes more than opportune. With the potential of the enumerated resources (natural, human, material, scientific and even financial ones, taking into account the European funds), multiple and successive integration, under synchronic, syncretic and synergic conditions (S^3) of the system elements, with emergent effect, i.e. in an **integronic** dynamics [Gruia R., 2013], may highlight a **model** with a good **bioeconomic** impact for the whole alimentary chain.

WORK METHODOLOGY

The system analysis has universal applicability. It makes possible the applicability of new theories and concepts. We mention out of these ones the theory of maximum power [Odum, H.T., 1984, Pillet, G., Odum, H.T., 1987] and the concept of emergetic sustainability [Gruia, R., 2002].

The analyses of systems, as the **alimentary system** is too, is a method resulted consequently to defining the theory and the notion of system. This concept, that helps to delimitate the field in which is developed the respective process, may be described by the formula:

$$S = \{X, Y, S_T/A\},$$

Where X represents the multitude of entrances, Y the multitude of exits, S_T the multitude of states and A the multitude of operations, or of transformations that the systems makes on entrances X to transform them in exits Y [Birlea St. 1975].

The state represents the values of the system fundamental parameters in a certain moment [Teodorescu, 1978, quoted by Gruia R., 2003], i.e. a succession of characteristic states of the respective system behavior. Thus, besides the analyses if economic efficiency, there may be also made analysis concerning the efficacy of the integrated system, at a level that may surprise implications unsuspected by the traditional economy, speaking here of bio economy. Such a demarche implies to apply the integronic management, by achieving a sustainable development of the integrated economic units, based on mechanisms on direction S_3 with emergent effect and it has the potentiality that, through polyvalent interferences, to settle the food act on bioeconomic principles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It is important to take into consideration social, economic and health perspectives, as for foods. International organizations, such as the United Nations (UN), Alimentation and Agriculture of the United Nations (FAO), the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OCDE) and the Health International Organization (OMS) are preoccupied to study, monitor and continuously improve the idea of "food - nutrition - health" all over the world, to

evaluate international prices of major and basic products, as well as to elaborate international policies and protocols concerning food security [Burtin, P., 2003, Agricultural Outlook 2010].

The „agri-zoo-food” sector for secure and healthy alimentation pursues the idea that a transition is necessary towards an optimum utilization of renewable and biologic resources, especially on direction of systems of production and primary processing (sustainable ones). Therefore, the food act as a whole will have to produce more aliments and other basic bioproducts, with entrances that reduce to minimum the impact upon the environment and the gas emission with glass house effect, as well as with improved ecosystem services, wastes approaching zero and adequate social value [Gruia R., 2003].

Consequently, an important step is the holistic approach of the food act, necessary in understanding the links within the system and, implicitly, variants of integration and development (taking also into account disintegration and evolution or involution). To this end we will take into consideration as necessary steps for multiple integrations, *the agri-forest-pasture system* in relation to the *agri-zoo-alimentary system*. The resultant of this interaction is to be found in fact at the basis of the food act regarded from bioeconomic perspective (fig.1).

Fig.1 – Block schema of bioeconomic type of systemic inter connexions sustaining the food act in integrative dynamics

From technologic and managerial point of view we distinguish the three integration level chain, which, in current acceptance, represent three distinct fields of the food act: agricultural engineering, food engineering and gastronomic engineering. If agriculture and food industry are fields with an old scientific, technologic and managerial basis, generally well known, as for gastronomy, the knowledge level is still in systemic organization and with a fragmentary scientific understanding and, not rarely, contradictory.

The shaping of the bioeconomic model of the food act will have to contain, as a complementary element, the elucidation of the gastronomic engineering demarche

[Gruia R., 2008], as well as complex connections between all the three integration levels of the analyzed system.

That is why we consider it opportune to systemically approach all these elements, highlighting **gastronomic engineering** analyzed in relation to the other components of the food act or from the perspective of the level of food elaboration (fig.2).

Fig.2. – Structural components of the food act, highlighting the complex impact of gastronomic sciences and techniques

Concerning the gastronomic engineering, the model may be shaped around the idea linked to *science and art in gastronomy*, where, in function of the origin of the used raw materials, we may speak about „gastronomic botanic”, „gastronomic zoology”, „molecular gastronomy" and „culinary constructivism”, aiming to establish and organize the exchange of knowledge and business in this field. Thus, there may be also structured scientific knowledge for social health and well being, without missing the present perspective, the bioeconomy, which expects to generate wealth and work [Hasler, F.M. 2002, Avalos García, A., and al. 2011; Gomez,A and al. 2012]

If, besides the typology of raw materials there are also taken into consideration elements of operational order, then the analyses of this part of the model may be structured in conformity with the schema from fig.3.

Fig.3 - Activity levels in operational techniques of gastronomic engineering

As it may be seen from what we have presented, the „core” of the food act is aliments with high complexity represented by **dishes and menus**, which need certain explanations and an attempt to define categories of aliments in function of their complexity.

It is known that the food notion means any product, in natural or processed state, that contains nutritive substances necessary to human organism and that is used to maintain its vital activity, not being harmful. Representations (some of them better known, others less known) concerning necessary characteristics to be taken into consideration in the systemic approach are those through which there may be identified the following types of foods. In table 1, foods to be found in the food / alimentary act have been grouped in 4 types of foods: primary, industrial, complex and hyper-complex ones, where „**unitary aliment**” with direct impact upon the organism is considered both dishes, and their combination within menus.

Table 1. TYPOLOGY OF FOODS PART OF THE FOOD ACT

No.	TYPE	DEFINITION	SUBCATEGORIES
1.	PRIMARY ALIMENTS	Practically represent „ <i>agricultural products</i> ”, i.e. soil products, animals, fish and products resulting from first transformation directly resulting from these products.	- classifications known from agriculture field
2.	INDUSTRIAL FOODS	Represent <i>de facto</i> „ <i>food products</i> ” obtained in food industry by later transformations than first transformation, respectively processing specific to food engineering that lead to obtaining in fact different preparations	<p>(a) « Processed » industrial foods: they are obtained by primary processing or standard fabrication in food industry or in the small farm industry (ex. cereals - flour; sunflower - oil; sugar beet - sugar etc.)</p> <p>(b) « Composite » industrial foods: they are alimentary products made in units of food industry based on a <i>recipe</i> (<i>preparation of an aliment using a receipt</i>), which represents a whole or an unit formed of several parts, respectively an association and/or a combination in a whole of several ingredients formed of raw agricultural material, out of which there is to be distinguished a basic component (matrix), armature elements and fibers for resistance, assuring an ensemble of materials that will confer characteristics that the every material in part DOES NOT have (ex.: bakery products, pastry ones, dairy products, salami and sausages products etc.).</p> <p>-----</p> <p>To distinguish:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - classical composite foods - functional composite foods = functional foods

3.	COMPLEX FOODS	They represent MIXED DISHES AND DRINKS that constitute a whole (based on culinary recipes), or a unit formed by several parts, i.e. a system gathering in itself several elements, respectively an association and/or a combination in a whole of several ingredients formed of raw agricultural material and/or from food industry; technologically they represent the use of a complicated combination of advanced preparation techniques, processes and cooking methods, using fresh ingredients (but, complementarily, also conserved ingredients), different textures and flavors, as well as innovative finishing and presentation techniques.	(a) classical complex foods
			(b) functional complex foods = « intelligent » culinary preparations
4.	HYPER-COMPLEX FOODS	They represent MENUS – they are represented by a group of culinary preparations served as a complete menu at a meal (breakfast, lunch, dinner etc.) representing dishes and drinks that form a whole or a unit formed of several parts, i.e. a system gathering in itself several elements, respectively an association and/or a combination in a nutritive whole („aliment”) of several ingredients formed of simple or composite raw food materials making a menu , i.e. food at a meal served at a given moment of the day.	(a) hyper-complex foods of classic menu type (b) hyper-complex functional foods of prophylactic, health-generating and dietetic menu type

Grouping the types of foods in function of the activity field, the types of made foods, but which are integrative pillars in the food act, they may be found as an inventory in table 2.

Table 2. CATEGORIES OF FOODS, AS PRODUCTS SPECIFIC TO THE FIELD OF CONNEX ACTIVITIES TO THE FOOD ACT

No.	ACTIVITY FIELD	CATEGORY OF PRODUCED ALIMENTS
1.	Classic food industry produces:	- processed foods; - composite foods;
2.	Health-generating food industry produces:	- functional foods; - nutraceuticals;
3.	Traditional nutritional gastronomy makes:	- classic complex foods (dishes and drinks based on culinary recipes); - hyper-complex foods (classic menus);
4.	Health-generating gastronomy and cuisine make:	- functional complex foods („intelligent” culinary preparations); - hyper-complex functional foods of prophylactic, health-generating and dietetic menu type.

Scale sizes are sizes completely characterized through a positive or negative number, as, for example, mass, density, volume, temperature, heat, etc., which is to be also found in parameterizing different types and categories of foods.

The main three types of control elements and indicators for scale values are: numerical; logical (booleene); alphanumeric (texts, strings, lines of characters). The interferences of scale elements have also as a result actions in the formation of gastronomic physico-chemical structures (fig.4)

Fig. 4 - Example concerning time and length scale in the formation of gastronomic structures

Structure on types of food categories and subcategories makes possible to pass to their parameterization from polyvalent perspectives, so that there may be analyzed integration phases and characteristics of the newly appeared systems along the alimentary chain. Certainly, here we are only stating a question, the process in itself presupposing a large investigation field in the future.

CONCLUSIONS

1. By applying *the integronic management* and achieving a sustainable development of integrated economic units, based on mechanisms on S^3 direction, with emergent effect, through polyvalent interferences, the food / alimentary act is set on bioeconomic principles.

2. *The food act* in its whole will have to produce more aliments and other basic bio products, with entrances that reduce at minimum the impact upon the environment and emission of gas with glass house effect, as well as with improved ecosystem services, wastes almost zero and appropriate social value; an integrative part of the alimentary act on bioeconomic direction are: agriculture, forestry, fishing and aquaculture, together with industries based on „bio concept”.

3. To take into consideration, as necessary steps for multiple integrations, the „*agri-forest-pastoral*” system in relation to the „*agri-zoo-food*” system, leads to interactions that stay at the basis of the alimentary act, where, from a technological and managerial point of view, we distinguish the chain of three integration levels, that represent, in current acceptance, three distinct fields of the alimentary act: agricultural engineering, food engineering and gastronomic engineering.

4. Foods to be found in the alimentary act are grouped in 4 types of foods: primary, industrial, complex and hyper-complex ones, where there are considered as „*unitary aliment*” with integronic interferences directly upon organism both aliments from food industry, and dishes and menus in their whole. Therefore, by structuring on types, categories and subcategories of foods it becomes possible to pass to their parameterization from polyvalent perspectives, so that there may be analyzed integration phases and the newly appeared characteristics along the alimentary chain.

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ROMANIAN BIOTECHNOLOGY THROUGHOUT TIME

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Abstract. *Although biotechnology is recognized as a separate branch of science and industry only of the late 20th century. Biotechnology through the oldest industrial processes has deep historical roots. Currently, as that the 20th century was the century of developing chemistry, in the 21st century biotechnology is one of the promoter sciences. In its history, Romania by known or anonymous researchers have contributed significantly to the development of modern biotechnology. This paper highlights Romania's contribution throughout time to the development of biotechnology*

Keywords: biotechnology, history, Romania

Introduction

The XXI century is the century of biotechnology, telecommunications and informatics as the twentieth century was dominated by the discoveries of physics, chemistry and biology. Although biotechnological processes are used from ancient times, the term "*biotechnology*" has been used according certain authors for the first time in 1910 by Thomas H. Morgan who proved that genes are carried by chromosomes and after others (the majority) by Karl Ereky in 1917 or 1919. Karl Ereky, defined biotechnology as "all lines of work by which products are produced from raw materials with the aid of living things" [2, 7].

Over the years, biotechnology has received various definitions, but currently is used mainly the definition adopted by the European Federation of Biotechnology and the European Commission, being as simple as just as comprehensive.

Thus, Biotechnology is the science that uses a live agent (microorganism, cellules, living part of the cell, enzymes.) to obtain products (antibiotics, dyes, enzymes, cheese, beer, wine, detergents, etc.) or services (pollution remediation, energy, metal mining,.) [22,23].

Biotechnology is extremely complex and covers virtually all areas of life. Today, as a result of intense industrial activity in the 19th and 20th centuries, as well as population growth has reached the point where mankind must solve a series of problems concerning the nature remediation and ensuring resources for human life. Consequently, at present is looking like through biotechnology,

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mankind to return to natural sources, to technologies which will be environmentally friendly.

From the historical perspective, biotechnologies are basically some of the oldest processes used by people to improve health, food and some services with deep roots in the most distant stages of development of human life on earth.

The main objective of this paper is to pursue the presence and development of biotechnologies along the Romanian history.

Biotechnology along the time

In this context the development of biotechnology can be divided into three main stages:

- Ancient Biotechnology
- Classical Biotechnology
- Modern biotechnology

Ancient Biotechnology

The longest period known in world history is the ancient one. It is comprised across thousands of years, from prehistory (over 10,000 î.e.n) until the early nineteenth century (≈1830).

Biotechnologies have begun with the first civilizations. The first sedentary populations, farmers and hunters realized empirically artificial selection, to obtain benefits such as larger fruit, resistant plants, larger animals, etc. or making products for health. The food processing is lost in the darkness of time. For example, old populations were observed that fruits and fruit juices fermented into wine, that milk could be converted into yogurt, buttermilk or cheese [19].

Data recorded on biotechnologies in the ancient world are extremely few, mostly represented by various discoveries in archeology. Thus, the best known are papyruses, clay tablets and Bible Bible which provided evidence that Sumerians and Babylonians produced beer with thousands years before Christ.

Archaeological research and a series of world renowned archaeologists show that the geographic area that is today Romania, was more than 10,000 years ago, hearth of the world, where human civilization really began [25, 26, 27, 27].

In this context, it is evident that the ancestors of the Romanians developed different aspect of biotechnology.

In 1961, archaeologist Nicolae Vlăssă, discovered three tablets, at a Neolithic site in the village of Tărtăria, Romania. The tablets are inscribed on only one side, and the inscriptions resemble a horned animal, a vegetal motif and a variety of mainly abstract symbols. Tablets dating is uncertain even if they were tested with carbon 14 due to contradictory stratigraphic evidence.

So, the tablets have been dated from around 6500 years ago, 5500 or even earlier at 7300 years old. However is wiser as a precaution to date the stones to 6000-5800 years ago. In any case, through images presented can conclude that

at that time lived in Romania farmers growing animals and plants (figure 1) [6, 12, 13, 17, 18].

Figure 1. Tărtăria tablets

The use of microorganisms in food processing is lost in the mists of time (bread, cheese, wine, beer). For example, Romanian ancestors grown vines in order to obtain the wine, at least 2000 years before Christ. De asemenea, istoria arata ca vita de vie, originara din Romania, a fost introdusa in cultivation in the valley of the Rhine and Moselle rivers between 276 and 282 after Christ by the emperor Probus Marcus Aurelius [11].

Using the gifts of nature in Dacia there were most outstanding known physicians of antiquity. Thus, Plato (427 B.C. – 347 B.C.), reveals a discussion between Socrates and Carmides, where Socrates explains that he had learned from a ‘Thracian’ doctor [9, 15].

Plant and animal sources have been used by humans for making clothing from time immemorial. In Romania, of textile fibers and animal material transmitted over millennia are found today in popular creations and newest creations in the fashion world. Thus, the renowned national blouses are now highly coveted worldwide. The original blouses are made from fine flax textile.

Over the thousand years, and continuing today, traditional pieces of folkloric art (from carpets to clothes) are being produced using flax fibers, hemp fibers or wool.

To obtain the desired textiles, hemp and flax were placed to melt in small pools landscaped alongside of the flowing water fords where specific microorganisms destroyed the pectin substances leaving available long cellulose fibers [3, 5].

Figure 2. The flax melting in small ponds near a river ford [29].

In the Middle Ages scientific development has entered into obscurity. Religious restrictions wars also, virtually permanent, made that development of science and hence of biotechnology to be an extremely low level.

However, during this period were mentioned some finds. For example in the China of the years 100 BC, chrysanthemum powder was used as insecticides. But, have to specify that such a preparation, although it was not mentioned in the documents, but was transmitted orally, was used by our ancestors for the same purpose.

The term "Ethanol" coined for the first time around the year 1150 by Paracelsus for the beverage obtained from distillation of beverages produced by fermentation.

It were attempted the first vaccinations against smallpox (1701, 1797), it was concluded that plants and animals alike reproduce in a sexual manner (1630), were described protozoa and bacteria and were recognized that such microorganisms might play a role in fermentation, it was used microscope to describe protozoa and bacteria and were recognized that such microorganisms might play a role in fermentation and was studied blood circulation in capillaries, described the nervous system as bundles of fibers connected to the brain by the spinal cord.

Advancements in the aspects concerning biotechnology in the Romania during the Middle Ages, are not registered. This is understandable if it is take into

account that this tumultuous period is marked by conflicts, wars and invasions of various nomadic peoples. Being on the eastern edge of Europe, Romania was the first country to which was kicked the invaders, against which the the country was forced to stand up to, to fight to protect the country and prevent their movement towards Western Europe.

Classical Biotechnology

Classical technology began to develop with the industrial revolution in the mid-1800s and it covered a large part of the nineteenth century, being carried on until the 1970s. This period is marked by adapting the known methods from all areas to industrial production. There are produced large quantities of food products and other materials in short amount of time. It developed various industries and intensive agriculture, processes that led to a large part of the problems facing mankind today. Many methods developed through classical biotech are widely used today. Biotechnology must find appropriate solutions to transform these traditional methods in the environmentally friendly means or at least with reduced pollution degree.

However the classical period is rich in numerous discoveries which are the basis for progresses of our days. Thus, it are achieved: advanced fermentation processes that allow better control, the use of predictable yeasts which led to modern baking industry; are discovered proteins, enzymes, penicillin, the structure of chromosomes and structure of nucleic acids; are developed methods for the production of ethanol by fermentation; acetone, acetic acid, butane, solvent dyes, etc. at level industrial; was introduced crop rotation; the first hybrid maize is performed; the discovery of the double helix structure of DNA resulted in an explosion of research in molecular biology and genetics, paving the way for the biotechnology revolution; the genetic code was "cracked" and was demonstrated that a sequence of three nucleotide bases (a codon) determines each of 20 amino acids and many others very important discoveries.

A large part of Romanian contributions to the development of biotechnology during this period are not known or are given a low importance. However, from the Romanian broad category of inventions, there are a number of discoveries / inventions that may be included in biotechnology.

So, the natural scientist Grigore Antipa, biologist, zoologist, ecologist and university professor, was the first who presented biological dioramas, a form of the framing nature in the cityscape (1907).

Ioan Cantacuzino, academician, doctor, microbiologist, university professor, has developed a cholera vaccination method, called "Method Cantacuzino", used today in countries where cholera cases can be observed, and in 1912 creates antityphique vaccine. He created the notion of immunity by contact. In the First World War he led the first massive cholera vaccination in the outbreaks of

infectious, saving many thousands of lives [30, 31]. As a result of his activity, the Professor Cantacuzino created, from legal point of view in 1921: « Serums and vaccines Institute "Dr. I. Cantacuzino"». But this will function as a state institute from 1924 and will have different sources of revenues such as those from the State budget, through the sale of vaccines and serums or donations [32].

Dr. Nicolae Paulescu discovered the insulin (1921), the hormone secreted by the pancreas that regulates the metabolism of carbohydrates, lipids, protids and minerals from the body. Dr. Paulescu is the one who has demonstrated efficacy of this substance in reducing the hyperglycemia and who used the insulin to treat diabetes. Unfortunately, due in part to historical conditions, after 8 months of publication in a Belgian specialized journal by Dr. Paulescu the results of his research under the title *Recherches sur le rôle du pancréas dans l'assimilation nutritive*”, two Canadians, who had taken notice of the Romanian work from the publications of the time, were able to isolate the insulin and use it to treat a patient, such as in 1922, so that in the 1922 they received the Nobel Prize for this discovery at the expense of Paulescu. In 1969, the Nobel Committee recognizes the merits and priority of N.C. Paulescu in the discovery diabetic treatment, but ruled out official repairing. “Official Repair” would have required significant material compensation [14, 30, 31].

Figure 3. Dr.Paulescu and insulin [32]

Emil Racoviță is the first biologist in the world who has studied life in Antarctica, he is the founder of biospeleology and discovered the beaked whale [8].

A spectacular discovery is *Gerovital*. Dr. Ana Aslan prepared this product in 1952 and it was patented in over 30 countries.

Figure 4. Emil Racovita and the Belgica ship [8]

In the same year she founded the *National Institute of Gerontology & Geriatrics „Ana Aslan”*.

Together with the pharmacist Elena Polovrageanu, Dr. Ana Aslan invents the geriatric *Aslavital* product too. Aslan therapy effects on aging were convinced from the start. Many famous patients (Tito de Gaulle, Pinochet, Chaplin, Claudia Cardinale, princesses, comtes, managers of the world's largest banks, etc.) came to treatment at *National Institute of Gerontology & Geriatrics „Ana Aslan”* from Otopeni.

Figure 5. Dr. Ana Aslan and Gerovital [30, 31]

Reputation of "Aslan" products known around the world, led to the worldwide setting up of clinics, hospitals and institutes specialized in using of Gerovital and derived products [30, 31].

In 1928/1929, Alexander Fleming discovered penicillin produced by *Penicillium* mould. However, industrial production of penicillin was developed only after the Second World War. With the help of chemical engineering processes were established methods of sterilization, cultivation, purification, concentration and conditioning of this first antibiotic. The discovery of penicillin led to the discovery and production of many antibiotics and other metabolites such as vitamins, hormones, enzymes, polyglucides, vaccines, monoclonal antibodies, alkaloids, gasoline, etc by using different kinds of microorganisms (bacteria, yeasts, moulds) [1, 4].

Thus, the period 1945 - 1970 is marked by the development and characterizing of microorganism's growth processes to produce at level industrial in the bioreactors whose capacity can reach values of 250,000 l.

In these circumstances in Iasi was built and opened in 1955, the first factory in Romania and South-Eastern Europe that has produced penicillin, had called the Chemical Factory nr. 2, Iasi. Four years later, as a result of diversifying the production of antibiotics and other medicines, the factory received the name of Antibiotics Factory. This factory is subsequently expanding its traditional portfolio becoming the most important producer of generic drugs and a brand with tradition (over 148 items), recognized in Romania with exports to over 73 countries worldwide [34].

Medical practice was developed as a result of the dedication of some doctors. For example Dr. Ioan Pop Popa is the first physician who performed open heart surgery from Romania, Dr. Marian Ionescu invented surgical equipment and artificial heart valves and Dr. Radu Deac invented as well artificial heart valves [35].

Develops wastewater treatment processes using microorganisms. For example Eng. George Volocvinschi is famous for inventing numerous technologies and systems with favorably impact through utility whereon it shows in terms of protecting the environment and their usefulness in everyday life [35].

In the period before 1990, Romania was difficult to have access to news published in scientific journals from developed countries such as those in Western Europe or the USA.

However, passionate scientists have published books focussed on biotechnology. For example, there were three Romanian reference books on obtaining enzymatic preparations, namely: Industrial Microbiology - D. Motoc, 1962; Technology and industrial applications of enzymes - I. Vasilescu 1963 and Bioengineering of microbial enzymatic preparations - G. Zarnea, Gh. Mencinicopschi, St. Bragarea, 1980.

Modern Biotechnology

Modern biotechnology is often considered as genetic engineering whose foundations were laid in 1800 with the first investigations on genes.

Genetic discoveries made in the nineteenth century made that biotechnology to develop accelerated after the 1970s. Scientific knowledges are becoming more thorough and advancements in their use and application are growing at least exponentially.

Practically, modern biotechnology is the fund for genetic engineering and development processes using enzymes or immobilized cells, enzymatic or cell bioreactors, bioreactors optimization, development of new bioreactors according to the needs of cell cultures or microorganisms, improve control, mathematical modeling, and process control through computers.

Modern biotechnology has applications in all areas of life: agriculture, bioremediation, light industry, chemical industry, food processing, health, food security and social development, energy, etc.

Since the 1980s, by manipulating genetic informattilor and using advanced microscopy and information technology are made stunning advances in the treatment of some genetic diseases, gene transfer is accomplished in mammals, human insulin is obtained using the bacterium *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) genetically modified, was cloned the first mammal (Dolly the sheep, 1996), technology developed Polymerase chain reaction (PCR), there was the first drug to treat a form of leukemia through genetic engineering - interferon (Roche, 1986), are obtained genetically modified crops (tomatoes, corn, soybeans .. - leader biotech firm Monsanto), the human genome is achieved through an international project, it establishes the method to create stem cell lines, was creates a recombinant vaccine for human papillomavirus (2006) and many others.

Many scientists worldwide have contributed to the amazing development of biotechnology of the last four decades. Romanian scientists' contribution, though not always mentioned, is appreciable. The causes of the lack of visibility of the contribution of Romania in biotechnology are mainly due to political regimes before and after 1990 which have given little real interest in research. As a result, a high number of Romanian scientists including biotechnologists, are working in various renowned institutions worldwide (ex: NASA, Cambridge) participating to important discoveries. It is important to note that annually tens of pupils, students win first places in international competitions and most are invited to attend renowned universities abroad and unfortunately most of them remain abroad.

However, despite the difficulties encountered, biotechnologists of different specialties have outstanding achievements, appreciated worldwide.

The best known example are the medals won by Romanian wines obtained through green technologies (Feteasca Neagra Egregio, Floare de Luna, Feteasca Neagra, Feteasca Alba, Grasa de Cotnari, Mosia de la Tohani, Origni Cabernet

Sauvignon, Sable Noble Alb, Solo Quinta White).

The discovery of the telocytes – a world first, made by a team of Romanian medical researchers from the Victor Babes National Institute of Pathology of Bucharest headed by Academician Laurentiu Mircea Popescu, who is the President of the Romanian Academy of Medical Sciences has been recognised in the United States too [20, 24].

A group of Romanian researchers have developed a technology for rapid regeneration of peripheral nerves (M. Albu, Professor I. Lascar, PhD. D. Zamfirescu, Acad. M. Simionescu, dr. I. Zegrea, dr. M. Popescu, I.D. Titorencu and G.Bumbeneci) for which at Trade Fair Innovations - Innova in Brussels in 2013, they received the gold medal [36].

Figure 6. The young researchers who represented the team and received their medal technology for rapid regeneration of peripheral nerves [37].

Doctors at the Institute Fundeni working on an artificial pancreas device (the size of a powder compacts, in which are implanted pancreatic cells). This objective is the attention of many researchers around the world but it is expected that this tool will be available only in the years 2017 - 2018 as it raises a number of issues concerning the speed of insulin action forms that will be used, reliability, convenience and accuracy of glucose monitors plus cybersecurity to protect devices from hacking [21].

Artificial blood, obtained by doctors at the "Babes-Bolyai" University of Cluj could get the Nobel Prize. Researchers who have conducted are skeptical about its realization in Romania [10].

Rodica-Mariana Ion - university professor and researcher at the Valahia University, specialist in porphyrin chemistry, and her team is the inventor of a new method of treatment of pre-malignant skin cancers [16].

The list could continue with other researchers from biotechnology, but the most remarkable are those who are involved in medical biotechnology as mentioned above.

Unfortunately, although Romania has enough smart minds able to meet the new challenges arising from population growth, antibiotic resistance or climate change, the real research is very little sustained. The funds are mainly for other than for applications in science, so in biotechnology. So if something does not change, inventions such as artificial blood or other will be taken, developed and promoted by interested institutions worldwide, and Romania will lose, like lost, for example Nobel Prize for the discovery of insulin.

Conclusions

Biotechnology is the science of today, of the future and it has its roots in the distant history. This science with its ramifications and roots in all exact sciences is meant to find solutions to the current problems of the world: healthy and safe food for the entire world population, non-invasive medical treatments, environmental pollution, green energy sources, climate change and many others.

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ORGANIC AGRICULTURE IN ROMANIA, TRENDS AND PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract. *Organic farming in Romania is considered a dynamic sector which recently has seen an upward trend. This paper through a three-dimensional shape that the production, distribution and marketing, pursued three levels based on the potentialities and performance levels of production perspective showing the organic sector nationally. The dimensional structure of the work was focused on the development and production areas in the dynamics of the last period. The indicators presented in physical and highlights current trends percentage of organic farming in Romania based on the evolutionary trends of the number of operators, the surface structure of the main crops, areas with potential for harvesting of spontaneous flora, the number of animals and the yields achieved. The form of interpretation is the result of an analysis of data from the annual level of indicators which showed a quantitative growth of production capacities (areas of crops and animal number), but also a qualitative side for on the one hand the possibilities of amplification production levels, and on the other manifestation of accelerated growth areas that can be harvested from the spontaneous flora. By dynamics values upward annual trend it may be seen a certain amplification of the organic farming activities at national level.*

Keywords: annual rate, ertified operators (in the agro-food sector), certified organic product, coefficient of variation, conversion, logo, ooganic agriculture, organic product, standard deviation

1. Introduction

Organic production issues in the current stage requires a special knowledge due to multiple interactions of the current socio-economic stage.

In this paper it is put into question the origin of products from organic farming which seeks a tridimensional knowledge of problems regarding the number and structure of the business operators, production capacity and yields obtained in organic farming.

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All of these issues analyzed nationally in the dynamics of the 2010-2014 pointed out the achievements, and, on this basis, specific indicators were calculated and analyzed.

The values of the indicators were expressed within differential forms in which, on one hand, it was played the amount expressed in physical units and also in percentage, and, on the other hand, the varying levels of probability given by the statistics.

The levels of these indicators highlights the trends and prospects of organic farming in Romania in an optimistic view.

2. Materials and methods

The national database was represented by the annual levels of 2010-2014 period [3] [4], which according to the used methodology were viewed in a different manner, but correlative. This is because the trends and prospects arising from this work are related to methods of solving, which are differentiated by the intensity of application in the territorial structure of organic farming.

The methodology was based on measurements commonly used in economics (indicators being expressed in concrete units of measurement and percentages) but also the interpretations drawn from the statistical indicators (average, standard deviation, coefficient of variation and annual rates). To interpret the indicators, there were followed specific structures at which the differences have been made on the forms regarding the certified organic / conventional systems. By these indicators, it was aimed to assess the competitiveness, making comparisons on the levels of studied temporal dynamics, and also the variation of the phenomena manifested in organic farming[2].

The methodology used in the paper aimed to highlight the elements of differentiation of the offer in the organic products market (pursuing the structural number of operators, surfaces and productions), played by appropriate indicators that can show / substantiate clearly the need and superiority effects of organic agriculture.

3. Results and discussions

The structure of this paper was gradually staged to respond to the current knowledge on the related issues, but also to the perspective development of organic farming in Romania. In this context, it was covered by a tridimensional sequential analysis including: recognizing the operators who can act in the organic food system; the potential and the actual capacities of organic production; the achievements of the ecological productions in the dynamic of these productions. All of these are shown both in the overall and in the production structure of animal and vegetal sectors whose interpretations are given by tables and graphs that substantiates particularly the organic farming trends and prospects nationwide.

3.1. Operators in the organic farming system in Romania

Preoccupations on organic farming and their results are focused primarily on the human factor which, in organic farming, is represented by the operators of this sector. Its structure is represented by producers, processors and traders, importers and

exporters, which have the role of intervention throughout the agri-food supply chain of organic products[1].

Mentioning particularly the growing number of processors, whereas the area under organic farming grows from year to year[6]. For the period 2010-2014, Table 1 presents the dynamics of the certified operators and organically farmed area in Romania, from which we can say the following:

- the number of certified operators has increased in an accelerated manner so that in 2012 it reaches a total of 14,470, being 4.58 times higher than in 2010. Still we can discuss the situation of 2012 and further where the number of registered operators is much higher (number being of 26,736 according to the situation shown in Fig. 1), but after completing the inspections carried out by inspection bodies and certification and granting certificates, their number is shrinking. At an average of 11,613 operators in the analyzed period it was found a standard deviation that measures the scattering elements examined of 4,147 and a coefficient of variation of 35.7 %, which reflects that the data series is not homogeneous, and in addition, the annual growth rate was 46.34 %;

- the increases regarding the operators number are much higher than the increase in the green area which causes the organic area / farmer to fall in differentiated rhythms. Thereby, the values provided by the standard deviation for the surfaces are much higher than the surfaces reported / operator (41.5 and 12.0 respectively), a situation that causes sharp variations for annual rates (by comparison the same indicators values are 12.7% and -23.3% respectively). To be noted that the coefficient of variation is inferior in the annual comparative analyzes of the overall organic surfaces (only 16.1%) compared to the surface per operator (which is 42.8%).

Table 1. Dynamics of the certified operators and organic farmed area in Romania for the period 2010-2014

Indicator	MU	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	Mean	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation (%)	Annual rate (%)
Number of certified operators in organic farm	No.	3.155	9.703	15.544	15.194	14.470	11.613	4.147	35.7	46.34
	%	100.	307.5	492.7	481.6	458.6	X	X	X	X
The total area in the organic farming	Th. ha	182.7	229.9	288.3	301.1	289.3	258.3	41.5	16.1	12.17
	%	100.0	125.9	157.8	164.8	158.3	X	X	X	X
Eco-area /operator	ha/operator	57.9	23.7	18.5	19.8	20.0	28.0	12	42.8	-23.3
	%	100.0	40.9	32.0	34.2	34.5	X	X	X	X

Source: Communications inspection and certification agency, Eurostat classification [3]

Fig.1. The number of registered operators in organic farming in Romania

Overall, it can be noted the yearly variational flow, which is due in particular to the existing support measures for the conversion period granted under Article. 68 of Regulation EC No. 73/2009 which establishes common rules for direct support schemes for farmers under the common agricultural policy and establishing certain support schemes for farmers.

Also it can be indicated that after the checks carried out by the certification and inspection agencies, only the operators who have complied with the rules of production will receive a certificate of organic product and will be able to label products with the words „green” by national sign "ae". It may be said that the label affixed to an organic product is required following the indications: reference to the organic production, logos, the name and code of inspection and certification agency which carried out the inspection and released the certificate of ecological product [1].

Next, referring to the organization of processing and marketing of the goods, it can be said that, in the current stage, this activity is an important element in the sector of organic farming. In the processing system it was created a structure specific to organic products. Exemplifying the situation of year 2012 (shown in Fig. 2), it appears that the most processing units are in the grain storage system (40.80%), honey and bee products (18.44%), pasta, flour and bakery products (7.76%), eggs packing (6.79%), spices and berries (5.82%).

Fig. 2. The structure of agri-food processing units in Romania
(Source: Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development).

Here it appears that the competitiveness of organic products is mainly determined by the number and structure of registered operators in this sector. At the current stage is carried out a continuously increase of the number of processors especially since the production potential of organic farm register increases from year to year. Regarding the marketing of organic products we can say that this is done only by registered traders to MADR, through various market channels: sales from the farm's gate, sales through wholesale stores, sales in specialized stores, sales in international market for green products (www.agricultura-ecologica.ro), seasonal sales in the markets [5, 8]

From all this, one can deduce that operators throughout the chain of production and distribution of an organic product must comply with applicable rules laid down in EU and national legislation. They must submit their work of visits conducted by inspection and certification agencies in order to compliance with the legal requirements for organic production.

3.2. Organic production capacities

Knowledge of organic production capacities (with reference to surface and livestock) is the key element, and incipient in the study of organic farming system. Of course, existing potentialities are certainly influenced by the socio-economic factors of each national territorial area. Referring to organically cultivated areas in Romania, it can be shown that they are still lower than the existing possibilities. By comparison with major European countries cultivators, the situation shown in Fig. 2 we can see that Romania is far below possibilities.

Fig. 3. Surface in organic farming in Europe, year 2011, MU: Ha
(Source: Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development).

This causes that further, in the dynamics of the years 2010-2014, to be analyzed the areas (in the structure of main crops) and livestock (for main species).

The structure of organic crops from Romania is illustrated in Table 2, where it follows a differentiated level of cultures, but also an increase in the total area under cultivation. It is worth mentioning that grain, which is prevalent, records a significant annual growth rate. With significant areas can be mentioned pastures and hayfields crops but in the latter part of the period considered are registered declines.

Table 2. Structure of organic crops in Romania for the period 2010-2014*

Crops	2010		2011		2012		2013		2014	
	Th.ha	%	Th.ha	%	Th. ha	%	Th.ha	%	Th. ha	%
I. The total area under organic crops	182.7	100.0	229.9	100.0	288.3	100.0	301.1	100.0	289.3	100.0
Gains	72.3	39.6	79.2	34.4	105.1	36.5	109.1	36.2	102.5	35.4
Dried pulses and protein crops	5.6	3.0	3.1	1.4	2.8	1.0	2.4	0.8	2.3	0.8
Tuberculifere plants and roots	0.5	0.3	1.1	0.5	1.1	0.4	0.7	0.2	0.6	0.2
Industrial crops	10.3	5.7	4.8	2.1	11.1	3.8	13.2	4.4	13.5	4.7
Plants harvested green	10.3	5.7	4.8	2.1	11.1	3.8	13.2	4.4	13.5	4.7
Other crops on arable land	0.6	0.3	0.9	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0
Vegetables	0.7	0.4	0.9	0.4	0.9	0.3	1.1	0.4	1.9	0.7
Permanent crops (orchards and vineyards)	3.1	1.7	4.2	1.8	7.8	2.7	9.4	3.1	9.4	3.3
Permanent crops (pastures and meadows)	31.6	17.3	78.2	34.0	105.8	36.7	103.7	34.4	95.7	33.1
Fallow land	10.2	5.6	9.8	4.2	8.8	3.1	9.5	3.2	9.1	3.1
II. Collection from spontaneous flora	77.3	X	338.1	X	1082.1	X	944.5	X	1787.5	X

Source: Communication of inspection and certification bodies; * Eurostat Classification

Figure 4 summarizes the evolution of those areas, the adjusted trend line is represented/contoured by the linear function ($y = 28.44x - 56.963$), being based on the growth trend and the level of correlation ($r = 0.89$).

Fig. 4. Evolution of the total surfaces placed in organic crops from Romania, period 2010-2014

The analysis is further illustrated by the evolution of the areas that are exemplified in the dynamics of the period 2010-2014. By using appropriate statistical indicators it is given the possibility of an analysis amplification of the existing structure, are characterized the level and the evolution of these surfaces. From those mentioned, it can be highlighted the following:

Table 3. Evolution of crop areas in Romania *

Crops	MU	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	Mean	Standard deviation	Coef. of variation (%)	Annual rate (%)
I. The total area under organic crops	Th.ha	182.7	229.9	288.3	301.1	289.3	258.3	41.5	16.09	12.17
	%	100.0	125.9	157.8	164.8	158.3	x	x	x	x
Grains	Th.ha	72.3	79.2	105.1	109.1	102.5	93.6	14.3	15.31	9.13
	%	100.0	109.5	145.4	150.9	141.8	x	x	x	x
Dried pulses and protein crops	Th.ha	5.6	3.1	2.8	2.4	2.3	3.2	0.9	28.72	-19.68
	%	100.0	56.6	49.7	43.1	41.6	x	x	x	x
Tuberculifere plants and roots	Th.ha	0.5	1.1	1.1	0.7	0.6	0.8	0.2	28.05	5.59
	%	100.0	213.1	223.0	146.9	124.3	x	x	x	x
Industrial crops	Th.ha	10.3	4.8	11.1	13.2	13.5	10.6	2.4	22.83	6.92
	%	100.0	46.4	107.3	127.7	130.7	x	x	x	x
Plants harvested green	Th.ha	10.3	4.8	11.1	13.2	13.5	10.6	2.4	22.83	6.92
	%	100.0	46.4	107.3	127.7	130.7	x	x	x	x
Other crops on arable land	Th.ha	0.6	0.9	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.4	0.3	83.30	-52.35
	%	100.0	146.9	4.8	45.5	5.2	x	x	x	x
Vegetables	Th.ha	0.7	0.9	0.9	1.1	1.9	1.1	0.3	29.61	27.30
	%	100.0	124.5	122.1	145.4	262.6	x	x	x	x
Permanent crops (orchards and vineyards)	Th.ha	3.1	4.2	7.8	9.4	9.4	6.8	2.5	37.14	32.17
	%	100.0	134.7	251.6	303.9	305.2	x	x	x	x
Permanent crops (pastures and meadows)	Th.ha	31.6	78.2	105.8	103.7	95.7	83.0	22.5	27.10	31.94
	%	100.0	247.6	335.1	328.4	303.0	x	x	x	x
Fallow land	Th.ha	10.2	9.8	8.8	9.5	9.1	9.5	0.4	4.54	-2.96
	%	100.0	95.5	86.2	93.1	88.7	x	x	x	x
II. Collection from spontaneous flora	Th.ha	77.3	338.1	1082.1	944.5	1787.5	845.9	510.6	60.36	119.29
	%	100.0	437.4	1400.0	1222.0	2312.6	x	x	x	x

Source: Communications inspection and certification agency; * Classification from Eurostat

-the total area occupied by the organic crops for the period under review is in constant growth, the annual average being 258.3 thousand hectares, and the comparison of last year 2014 compared to 2010 showed an increase of + 58.3%. Standard deviation (as difference compared to the average) is by 41.5, and

coefficient of variation through 16.09% level characterizes a homogenous series, and the annual growth rate in the period under review which is of 12.17%;

-levels of crop area size can be structured as follows: cereals, industrial crops, plants harvested green and permanent crops, which in 2010 recorded the largest areas (between 10.3 and 72.3 thousand hectares), these crops recording also the most significant growth rates; with relatively low areas crops such as vegetables, dried and protein crops, other crops on arable land whose surface is also small, but also decreasing, so that annual rate is negative; vegetable culture which can be said that occupies reduced areas but registering continues annual growth with an annual growth rhythm of 27.30%;

-collection from spontaneous flora valued at surface harvested records the largest surfaces, but also the highest growth rate (119.29%). Annual oscillations, though rising, are very high which is why the standard deviation and coefficient of variation recorded the highest values (510.6 and 60.36% respectively).

The livestock sector, part of the organic farm, is considered a continuation of production capacity, which in this paper covers the main livestock species. The livestock on which was done the production possibilities analysis referred to the following categories: dairy cattle, sheep and goats, hens, pigs, beehives. For the period 2000-2014, the livestock structure is shown in Table 4, and on this basis, the interpretations are concentrated on the values of the calculated indicators from which it can deduct the following:

- The existence of differences in annual herd structures, namely: dairy cows, sheep and goats and chickens hens are registered in all the analyzed years (excluding 2000 for laying hens); for swine herds and beehives are only records from 2014;

- The actual records for the 2000-2014 period are obvious: additional herd trends, so in 2014 compared to 2000 the increase is 16.0 times for dairy cows and 71.3 times for sheep and goats, and for hens in comparison to 2003, the growth is 20.8 times;

- For the same categories of livestock (dairy cows, sheep and goats, laying hens) interpretations of statistical indicators are presented in the following form: the standard deviation and coefficient of variation are given by values with a degree of scattering high in which case they are considered non-homogeneous series; annual growth rate in percent is very significant (if the dairy cows is only 48.7%, in laying hens level reaches 131.9%).

Table 4. Evolution of the number of animals reared in organic farming in Romania (p. 16)*

Product	UM	2000	2003	2007	2014	Mean	Standard deviation	Coef. of variation (%)	Annual rate (%)
Dairy cows	nr.	2100	7200	6265	33782	9780.8	6030	61.7	48.7
	%	100.0	342.9	298.3	1608.7	X	X	X	X
Seep and goat	nr.	1700	3200	78076	121283	37542.3	43228	115.1	84.0
	%	100.0	188.2	4592.7	7134.3	X	X	X	X
Chickens hens	nr.	-	2000	4720	57797	14303.4	17397	121.6	131.9
	%		100.0	236.0	2889.9	X	X	X	X
Swine	nr.	-	-	-	126	X	X	X	X
Beehives	nr.		...		81.58	X	X	X	X

Source: Preliminary research ... (conf. www.maap.ro, accessed on 12.12.2008); Report stage - Stage I Period: October 1 2008-15 January 2009 CONSUMECO no. 92-075 / 1.10.2008

Regarding the image of the organic production capacity in Romania, we can observe a certain annual increase, along with a differentiation in the structure of crop / animal categories, situation supplemented by annual fluctuations that determine rates of annual variation differentiated.

3.3. Productions obtained in organic farming in Romania

Productions made in organic farming represents a qualitative element that complements the knowledge of the situation at national level. The analysis was carried out for the total production achieved, but on the average levels of the main organic crops.

The evolution of total productions made in organic system, presented in Table 5, are played by the quantitative structure of plant products, livestock and processed.

The dynamic levels presented for the period 2000-2007 in absolute and relative terms, are supplemented with statistical indicators by which performance can be highlighted the following aspects:

Table 5. Evolution of the yields obtained in organic farming in Romania

Specification	UM	2000	2003	2005	2007	Mean	Standard deviation	Coef of variation (%)	Annual rate (%)
1.- Crop production									
The total amount of vegetable. from which:	t	13,502	30,400	131,898	169,312	81,948	56,798	69.3	43.5
	%	100	225.15	976.87	1253.97				
Grains	t	7,200	14,400	55,000	65,127	32,459	19,934	61.4	37.0
	%	100	200	763.88	904.54				
Oilseed and protein	t	5,500	12,480	45,600	52,982	30,606	21,561	70.4	38.2
	%	100	226.90	829.09	963.30				
Vegetables	t	600	2,000	7,200	3,410	4,115	1,919	46.6	28.2
	%	100	333.33	1,200	568.33				
Fruits	t	-	300	1,000	1,255	599	352	58.8	44.4
	%	-	100	333.33	418.33				
Gathering wild flora	t	200	320	16,748	35,236	10,333	11,487	111.2	109.3
	%	100	160	8,374	17,618				
Other cultures	t	2	900	6,350	11,302	3,987	4,183	104.9	243.6
	%	100	45,000	317,500	565,100				
2.- Livestock production									
Cow milk	hl	58,367	92,485	100,000	85,031	88,423	14,496	16.4	5.5
	%	100	158.45	171.32	145.68				
Sheep milk	hl	701	1470	13,500	13,273	6,168	5,942	96.3	52.2
	%	100	209.70	1,925.82	1,893.43				
Eggs	Th. pcs	-	500	1820	1321	1,073	399	37.1	27.5
			100	364	264.2				
3.- Main products processed									
Sheep cheese	t	18	45	480	510	213	218	102.3	61.2
	%	100	250	2,666.66	2,833.33				
Schweitzer	t	23	110	268	580	225	188	83.6	58.6
	%	100	478.26	1,165.21	2,521.73				
Pressed cheese	t	-	220	330	640	351	166	47.3	32.0
	%		100	150	290.90				
Canned vegetables and fruits	t	-	-	50	40	42	4	83.8	4.6
	%	-	-	100	80				
Honey	t	10	110	610	1950	543	543	100.1	112.4
	%	100	1,100	6,100	19,500				

Source: Organic farming component of the green economy, www.economia-verde.ro/;
Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development

- Crop production is distinguished by a relevant annual increase (for total crop in 2007 compared to 2000 registered an increase of 1,253.27% and in cropping patterns can be highlighted quantities obtained from wild flora and group of other cultures). Standard deviation levels signifies the highest degree of scattering of the total quantities, followed by cereals, oilseeds and vegetables. Referring to the coefficient of variation as an indicator of data scattering and of the growth rate dynamics may nominate quantities harvested and the products of spontaneous group of other cultures (values are 112.2 and the standard deviation of 14.9% and

for the annual rate of 109.3 and 234.6% respectively);

- animal production frames the same annual growth oscillations, situation which is embossed on all products by comparing the years 2007/2000, with special reference to sheep milk as an increase in 2007 of 18.9 times. Simultaneously the cow milk product has the highest standard deviation value (14,496). Further comparison of variability based on the coefficient of variation and the annual rate analysis, at the production of sheep milk is found the existence of the highest rates (96.3% and 52.2% respectively) which meant a high level of dependence towards the terms of past years;

- The evolution analysis of annual quantities of main products processed for the period 2000-2007 is represented by significant annual increases for most of these products. The level and variation in terms of all the products concerned we can notice the sheep cheese and honey. For these products are registered maximum values for the standard deviation (218 and respectively 543), the coefficient of variation (102.3% respectively 100.1%) and average rate (61.2% and 112.4%) for these products taking into consideration the definite perspective trend of quantitative growth and annual rhythms.

Plotted the evolution of total vegetal production t shown in Fig. 5 is shown by an upward line resulting from the linear regression function ($y = 25.129x - 50.258$), along with a growth correlation report very significant ($r = 0.95$).

Fig. 5. The total vegetal production evolution in organic system in Romania, 2000-2007

The evolution of average productions in organic farming in Romania is an interpretive indicator whose importance is given not only by the development level of these yields, but also by the results in comparison to other systems commonly practiced in agriculture (non-organic). For the period 2007-2011 these productions were analyzed in comparison quantitatively / percentage, but also in terms of significance represented by the statistics relating to variations in annual rates. The data presented in Table 6 representative accumulate all these problems

of average productions for wheat, cabbage, tomatoes and wine grapes, it can be highlighted the following:

Table 6. The average production evolution achieved in the organic agriculture in Romania, 2007-2011

Specification	UM	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	Mean	Standard deviation	Variation coef. (%)	Annual rhythm (%)
Wheat	kg/ha	1,541	3,403	2,421	2,688	3,663	2,743	632	23.0	24.1
	%	100.0	220.8	157.1	174.4	237.7	X	X	X	X
Cabbage	kg/ha	19,364	19,680	20,724	20,858	21,807	20,487	772	3.8	3.01
	%	100.0	101.6	107.0	107.7	112.6	X	X	X	X
Tomatoes	kg/ha	12,916	15,814	15,395	15,443	17,602	15,434	1,023	6.6	8.05
	%	100.0	122.4	119.2	119.6	136.3	X	X	X	X
Wine grapes	kg/ha	5,537	6,275	6,255	5,155	5,649	5,774	393	6.8	0.50
	%	100.0	113.3	112.9	93.1	102.0	X	X	X	X

Source: Organic farming component of the green economy, www.economia-verde.ro/; Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development

- At all crops we can see annual levels amplified in years, considering significant increases in wheat and tomatoes (resulting from the comparison report 2011/2007 amplifications of the average production level of 37.7% and 36.3%);

- Annual variations in average yields expressed by statistical indicators still reveal a high level of standard deviation at wheat and tomatoes (these values were 632 and 1.023). The coefficient of variation analysis and the annual rate is significant for the wheat crop yields obtained (these values being 23.0% and 24.1%), means by comparison a variability (with homogeneous character), but also an increase from a unit interval to another. Crops of cabbage and grapes for wine the coefficient of variation and the annual rate have values close to the lower limit, so both a low amplitude, and an insignificant increase.

The graphics of the evolutionary level of average production for grains shown in Fig. 6 resulting from the linear function ($y = 345.67x + 692.135$) falls in the form of a linear growth. The correlation report ($r = 0.83$) signifies a strong correlation in the dynamic of years.

Fig. 6. The average productions /ha evolution for cereals grains organic cultivated in Romania, 2006-2012

One of the main problems especially in organic products marketing is the system of certification that producers must possess. The production system through organic certification is subject to the inspection and certification according to current standards[7]. But transformation costs from an usual farm to an organic farm are linked to certification of products, the market reorientation of products and retraining: retrofitting vehicles and machinery, converting land to meet the exclusion of herbicides and phytosanitary treatments[9].

Connected to this concern of total organic production is limited the organic certified production. In the records structure of organic products quantities from Romania, certified organic yields are at a lower level than at the general organic level. Analyzing the data presented in Table 7 on the evolution of average crops certified organic, can be highlighted the following:

Table 7. The average productions evolution for the certified crops in organic agriculture from Romania

Specification	UM	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	Mean	Standard deviation	Variation coef. (%)	Annual rhythm (%)
Cereals grains	kg/ha	1,218	2,583	2,252	2,652	2,911	2,324	471	20.3	24.34
	%	100.0	212.0	184.8	217.7	239.0	X	X	X	X
Cabbage	t/ha	13.5	15.7	14.5	14.6	15.2	14.7	0.616	4.2	3.01
	%	100.0	116.2	107.0	107.7	112.6	X	X	X	X
Tomatoes	t/ha	9.7	11.1	10.8	10.8	12.3	10.9	0.615	5.6	6.17
	%	100.0	113.6	110.6	111.0	127.1	X	X	X	X
Grapes for wine	kg/ha	3,258	3,752	3,758	2,927	3,486	3,436	275	8.0	1.71
	%	100.0	115.2	115.4	89.9	107.0	X	X	X	X
Apple	kg/ha	4,296	4,212	5,044	5,249	4,999	4,760	405	8.5	3.86
	%	100.0	98.0	117.4	122.2	116.4	X	X	X	X
Pear	kg/ha	2,067	2,605	2,338	3,895	3,595	2,900	676	23.3	14.83
	%	100.0	126.0	113.1	188.4	173.9	X	X	X	X

Source: Organic farming component of the green economy, www.economia-verde.ro/; Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development

- The productions yields obtained in years are increasing. By comparing the level of 2013 with 2007 there were increases of the analyzed crops between 7.0% and 139.0%;
- Annual variations are reported for these productions, so high levels for the standard deviation for most crops, a phenomenon that is effectively connected with the existence of annual growth of production;
- Coefficient of variation means annual increases productions considered homogeneous for all cultures;
- The annual growth rate is differentiated, so for the crops analyzed: high growth rates for grains and pear (24.34% and 14.83%), medium for cabbage, tomato and apple (3.01%, 6.17% and 3.68% respectively) and small increases in wine grapes (1.71%).

All questions arising from the analysis of organic production growth emerges a trend but subjected to manifested annual variations. This phenomenon is related on the one hand to the organizational aspect, and secondly the possibility of applying the most appropriate technologies.

Conclusions

From the pursued and achieved study through the indicators system for the 2000-2011 period can be summarized several issues relating to trends and prospects of organic farming in Romania.

(Conclusion 1) Increased number of organic operators (producers, processors and traders, importers and exporters) is justified at national level by the effective implementation aspect in all activities / works existing in the entire agro food chain of organic products. Today it is put the question of the necessity to respect the Community and national law on organic production and indications arising from inspection visits conducted by inspection bodies and certification.

(Conclusion 2) Organic production capacities increase in the vegetal sector (referring to crop areas) projecting growth rates standing alongside the existence of variations in levels of production capacity. The levels structure of these capacity, with reference to the area occupied by organic farming can be identified: cereal crops, industrial crops, plants harvested green and permanent crops that occupy the largest areas, but also the most significant growth rates; crops with relatively low surfaces such as dried legumes and protein crops, other crops on arable land whose surface is already low and decreasing, so that the annual rate is negative; vegetables grow on small areas but has a significant annual increase; collections of spontaneous flora evaluated at harvested area for which is registered the largest areas, but also the highest growth rate.

(Conclusion 3) Livestock sector (focused on the following categories: dairy cattle, sheep and goats, hens, swine, bees) indicates the existence of differences namely: dairy cows, sheep and goats and laying hens, are registered effectives in all years of the analyzed period (with the exception of 2000 for laying hens); for swine herds and beehives registers are only in 2014, having also increasing trends. For these animals the standard deviation and coefficient of variation values are represented by a very high degree of scattering, at which can be added a very significant annual growth.

(Conclusion 4) Vegetal production quantitatively analyzed registers growths, but which manifests differences in annual growth and crop structure (with significant increases in total crop production quantities obtained of spontaneous flora and group of other crops). For livestock it may be mentioned amounts related to milk sheep product who experienced the most significant growth (of 18.9 times in 2007 compared to 2000), together with the existence of the highest values of the

coefficient of variation and the annual rate . For the main products processed the levels evolution of annual quantities plays significant annual increases for most of these products (sheep cheese and honey, are recorded maximums and a definite trend growth).

(Conclusion 5) The average yields (falling within the general organic level) has growths in years (can be considered significant increases in wheat and tomatoes and the statistical indicators that reveal a high level). At crops of cabbage and white grapes for wine the coefficient of variation and the annual rate have values close to the lower limit, indicating both a low amplitude, and an insignificant increase.

(Conclusion 6) The certified organic average production situation indicates a lower level than the productions from the general organic level . Their production efficiency the in succession of years is increasing. Are reported annual changes with respect to the standard deviation that has high levels for most crops, but a differential annual growth rate (for the analyzed crops, can be identified: growth rates higher for grains and pear, medium for cabbage, tomato and apple and small increases in wine grapes).

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CURRENT COORDINATES REGARDING THE AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION POSIBILITIES AND THE FOOD CONSUMPTION IN ROMANIA

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Abstract. *The paper aims to synthesize the main aspects related to the agricultural production and food consumption in Romania. The analysis performed presents the main groups of agricultural food products (cereals, sunflower, sugar beet, vegetables, fruits, meat, milk, and eggs), at which are envisaged the production and the consumption.*

Nationally, under a three-dimensional form are detailed aspects that concern the following: achievable and usable production, current food consumption, value equilibriums of resources/consumption balance in the food system. Indicators expressed in absolute and relative values reflect the current situation that through the annual comparative forms of 2008-2014 dynamics reveal the overall and the achievement possibilities, along with the qualitative aspect that regards the structure for the main groups of agricultural products. From this paper it emerges the amplification trend of food products quantities, justified through the requirements that are becoming more complex and diverse.

Keywords: food consumption, production usable synthetic indicators of variation (standard deviation, coefficient of variation, annual rhythm, correlation, linear regression function).

1. Introduction

Food production is one of the human activities that generate the greatest resource of consumption and pollution. In the system of consumption, it may be mentioned that the latest consumers reviews relate mainly to: information, quality, technology and production systems, which constantly have to prove respect for the environment and, not least, fairness in the application of

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technologies in production and distribution of two-dimensional system.

Nowadays, the role and importance of consumer increase in whole-food sector. The increasing demand for food is one of the major causes that determine the steady increase agricultural yields and thus deforestation. With the increasing demands and requirements of their food products to these products are becoming more complex and diverse. Consumers want to eat healthy and cheap food, corresponding to the requirements and preferences of each one, questioning the quality of these products [6].

Another aspect of studying consumption approached by economists refer to the costs of satisfying those requests, basically the cost of productions reported to the final price.

In this context, the task of particular interest is to recognize the trends manifesting in the current period in terms of food consumption. Those are the most important reasons for whom studying consumption is an important component of any market research [5].

Through this paper it is seeking the knowledge of national trends demand of food products whose rhythm is growing as one of the major causes that determine the steady growth of agricultural crops. The issue is that in the system production / consumption there are permanent irregularities related to agri-food production possibilities default and structure of consumption. There are two dimensional production / use regarding the quantitative aspect which seek the overview and the practicability, along with the qualitative aspect of the structure of production and consumption. Quantities of foods consumed increased and consumer demand to these products are becoming more complex and diverse.

2. Materials and methods

The methodology used in this paper is based on the statistical data available in official documents at national level on 2008-2014. Production and consumption were focused both main vegetable products (total cereal grains, sugar beet, potatoes, vegetables, fruits) and animal products (meat, milk, wool and eggs). The data processing was focused on the emerging structure of specific indicators, expressed in concrete units (production / consumption per citizen), conventional units (calories / protein per citizen) but as value (levels of income / working expenses of households, supplemented by total consumption expenditure structure). The evolution of production /

consumption completed the current overview level of knowledge in a national perspective.

The interpretations were performed by comparisons of indicators expressed as a percentage share of the total consumption compared to 2008, considered basic in dynamics annual periods. The calculation of deviations in production / consumption per capita for the main products analyzed was performed by calculating the standard deviation, variation coefficient, rhythm of the year for each month and correlation report. Level emerged expressed in concrete units and the percentage of those indicators defines the possibilities of food production and consumption trends, and correlations production↔consumption that can be created[2].

In order to determine the trend of the statistical link were used estimative equations corresponding to the analytic function expressed as the relationship between the characteristic factor (output) and the resultant (consumption) by plotting the regression function (which is given by the line / curve regression type $ax^2 + bx + c = y$)[1]. Values arising from the use of regression functions have played as statistical / mathematical variation levels that emerged from the production / consumption oscillations.

The evolutionary shape of the relationships of these correlations and production / consumption reports was presented graphically based on the variation details.

The synthesis of all of these is presented in tables and graphs that, through an appropriate form substantiates the production and consumption possibilities in Romania.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Agricultural production feasible and usable in Romania

Agricultural and agro-food production has to be seen in the implications on food consumption regardless of the territorial area analyzed. For Romania food production/consumption system is a permanent exchange of views that can be fit in optical of food policies through an analysis based on levels of the main productions per capita. Territorial, for Romania it is necessary a knowledge that can be rendered as the production realized / used per capita, analysis deepened by a structural comparison of the dynamics of the years 2008-2014. On its output per capita, shown in Table 1 and the annual growth in product structure can be seen:

Table 1. Production achieved by the main products per capita in Romania

Specification	MU	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Grain cereals	kg	819.3	730.2	825.5	1034.5	639.3	1045.7	1108.6
	% 2008	100	89.12	100.75	126.26	78.03	127.63	135.31
Sunflower	kg	57.0	53.9	62.4	88.8	69.7	107.2	110.0
	% 2008	100	94.56	109.47	155.78	122.28	188.07	192.98
Sugar beet	kg	34.4	40.1	41.4	32.8	35.9	51.5	70.2
	% 2008	100	116.56	120.34	95.34	104.36	149.70	204.06
Potatoes	kg	177.7	196.6	162.2	202.3	122.9	164.6	176.8
	% 2008	100	110.63	91.27	113.84	69.16	92.62	99.49
Vegetables	kg	186.0	191.6	190.8	207.3	176.2	198.2	191.0
	% 2008	100	103.01	102.58	111.45	94.73	106.55	102.68
Fruits	kg	57.4	65.0	70.1	73.5	56.3	65.1	65.4
	% 2008	100	113.24	122.12	128.04	98.08	113.41	113.93
Meat*	kg	64.9	70.8	64.5	67.4	66.4	65.0	66.1
	% 2008	100	109.09	99.38	103.85	102.31	100.15	101.84
Milk	liters	287.3	276.8	242.7	248.5	241.0	243.8	253.8
	% 2008	100	96.34	84.47	86.49	83.88	84.85	88.33
Wool	kg	1.1	1.1	1.0	0.9	1.0	1.0	1.1
	% 2008	100	100	90.90	81.81	90.90	90.90	100
Eggs	piece	326	305	306	314	319	320	333
	% 2008	100	93.55	93.86	96.31	97.85	98.15	102.14

*) Calculations for the weight of live animals slaughter for consumption Source (basic calculation): Romanian Statistical Yearbook 2014, INS [3, 4]

- Annual production variation fall differentiated rhythms, finding a predominance of growth trend;
- Compared to 2008 increases per capita, these productions are different, finding very sharp increases in grain, sunflower and sugar beet (comparative values are between 135.31% and 204.06%) and also below levels compared to year 2008 for potatoes and milk (from 99.49% to 88.33%);
- Levels of achieved productions with very small variations (considered stagnation) are registered at products: vegetables, fruits, meat, wool and eggs.

Hence the conclusion of the existence of differentiated levels in achieving annual production, the trends being oscillatory.

Production used per capita interests the flow analysis performed because has those quantities of primary products produced during the reference period, including amounts used by producers from their own production (self-consumption) and / or quantities of processed products (not included losses in the production process). Nationally, the values shown in table 2 outlines in the structure of the products studied the following aspects:

Table 2. Usable production for main products per capita in Romania

Specification	MU	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Cereals	Th.tons	16678	14723	16534	20619	12620	20569	21715
	% 2008	100	88.27	99.13	123.63	75.66	123.33	130.20
Vegetables	Th.tons	3882	3955	3925	4253	3599	3955	3874
	% 2008	100	101.88	101.10	109.55	92.70	101.88	99.79
Fruits	Th.tons	2189	2313	2160	2359	1875	2292	2085
	% 2008	100	105.66	98.67	107.76	85.65	104.70	95.24
Meat	Th.tons	1013	1045	946	976	965	940	956
	% 2008	100	103.15	93.38	96.34	95.26	92.79	94.37
Milk	Th.tons	6687	6406	5710	5789	5628	5651	5877
	% 2008	100	95.79	85.38	86.57	84.16	84.50	87.88
Eggs	Th.tons	335	311	310	316	320	319	332
	% 2008	100	92.83	92.53	94.32	95.52	95.22	99.10

Source (basic calculation) : Romanian Statistical Yearbook 2014, INS [3, 4]

- Variations in the annual level, the comparative oscillations to year 2008 are between 84.16% and 130.20 %;

- Annual variations in the products structure highlights: annual percentage increases that are only recorded for cereals (and this only for the period 2011-2014), stagnating levels in vegetables and fruits, and an effective decrease for animal products.

Of the presented, it is shown that usable production levels compared to the achieved production levels are in an annual decrease tendency, finding an emphasis on animal products.

3.2. Current food consumption

Since permanently the existence of most agricultural production is influenced by the permanent human consumption, the main concern is the human consumption. Analysis of national human food consumption is presented in a three dimensional presentation as: kg product / capita, no. calories/capita and protein grams/capita. Human consumption per capita in kg product/capita is played through dynamic comparative period 2008-2012 presentation made in absolute and relative figures. According to values in Table 3 can be deduced the following:

- Per capita consumption for vegetal products registers annual variations, with an increasing trend (growth rates of 2014 compared to 2008 are between 1.52 % and 20.24 %) ;

- For the main livestock products the annual oscillation are constant but annual in comparison to 2008, annual levels recorded a downward trend (of 2014 compared to 2008 levels are between - 8.56 % and -4.12 %) .

Table 3. Human consumption per capita in kg, product / capita in Romania.

Specification	MU	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Cereals	kg/pers.	204	200.8	199.6	205.4	208.5	218.5	207.1
	% 2008	100	98.43	97.84	100.68	102.20	107.10	101.52
Vegetables	kg/pers.	176	168.2	174.4	181	177.4	180.7	182.9
	% 2008	100	95.56	99.09	102.84	100.79	102.67	103.92
Fruits	kg/pers.	66.7	62.3	63.3	70.5	71.1	73.7	80.2
	% 2008	100	93.40	94.90	105.69	106.59	110.49	120.24
Meat	kg/pers.	66.6	62.3	60	56	58.7	57.5	60.9
	% 2008	100	93.54	90.09	84.08	88.13	86.33	91.44
Milk	kg/pers.	262.3	240.2	230.7	234.5	241.1	244.5	251.5
	% 2008	100	91.57	87.95	89.40	91.91	93.21	95.88
Eggs	kg/pers.	13.4	12.2	12	12.5	12.3	12.4	12.3
	% 2008	100	91.04	89.55	93.28	91.79	92.53	91.79

Source (basic calculation): Romanian Statistical Yearbook 2014, INS [3, 4]

Considered an analytical indicator human consumption expressed in no. calories / capita is analyzed in the same dynamic, the expression is carried out in absolute and relative values.

The data in Table 4 for consumption categories of vegetal and animal products expressed in calories reveals the same trend, namely:

- Increasing the number of calories for vegetal products (between + 0.64 % and + 9.63 %);
- Reducing the number of calories for animal products (between -8.92% and -3.96 %)

Table 4. Human consumption per capita in no. calories / capita.

Specification	MU	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Cereals	No. calories/ pers.	1299	1280	1268	1309	1323	1389	1321
	% 2008	100	98.53	97.61	100.77	101.84	106.92	101.69
Vegetables	No. calories/ pers.	156	145	146	153	156	154	157
	% 2008	100	92.94	93.58	98.07	100	98.71	100.64
Fruits	No. calories/ pers.	135	119	119	132	133	138	148
	% 2008	100	88.14	88.14	97.77	98.51	102.22	109.63
Meat	No. calories/ pers.	303	306	278	259	271	265	276
	% 2008	100	100.99	91.74	85.47	89.43	87.45	91.08
Milk	No. calories/ pers.	481	441	424	430	443	449	462
	% 2008	100	91.68	88.14	89.39	92.09	93.34	96.04
Eggs	No. calories/ pers.	63	57	56	58	58	58	59
	% 2008	100	90.47	88.88	92.06	92.06	92.06	93.65

Source (basic calculation): Romanian Statistical Yearbook 2014, INS [3, 4]

Further human consumption per capita in protein grams / inhabitant is assessed according to the same structure. The data outlined in Table 5, present in vegetal and animal products structure the following:

Table 5. Human consumption per capita expressed in grams protein / capita.

Specification	MU	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Cereals	grams proteins/pers.	39.3	38.7	38.4	39.6	40.1	41.9	39.8
	% 2008	100	98.47	97.70	100.76	102.03	106.61	101.27
Vegetables	grams proteins/pers.	7.7	7.2	7.1	7.5	7.8	7.6	7.7
	% 2008	100	93.50	92.20	97.40	101.29	98.70	100
Fruits	grams proteins/pers.	2.2	1.7	1.7	1.8	1.8	1.9	2
	% 2008	100	77.27	77.27	81.81	81.81	86.36	90.90
Meat	grams proteins/pers.	26.3	26.8	23.8	22.1	23.3	22.8	24.3
	% 2008	100	101.90	90.49	84.03	88.59	86.69	92.39
Milk	grams proteins/pers.	25.2	23	22.1	22.5	23.1	23.5	24.1
	% 2008	100	91.26	87.69	89.28	91.66	93.25	95.63
Eggs	grams proteins/pers.	5.1	4.7	4.6	4.8	4.7	4.7	4.7
	% 2008	100	92.15	90.19	94.11	92.15	92.15	92.15

Source (basic calculation): Romanian Statistical Yearbook 2014, INS [3, 4]

- Cereals products recorded increasing rhythms, referring to the second half of the reviewed period (the growth rate of 2014 compared to 2008 is 1.27 %);

- For vegetables, the annual oscillations recorded very small decrements in most years, that may consider stagnating levels over time;

- For fruits and all animal products the decreasing consumption is certain for all years of the period analyzed (by comparison of 2014 versus 2008 decreases between -4.37% and -9.10 %).

Comparing the systems of human consumption it may be seen a variation of annual level, concomitant with trends which can be identified:

a) consumption increases for vegetal products and concomitant decreases in animal products expressed as kg. products/ capita;

b) less significant increases maintaining approximately the same level, but with concomitant decrease for all animal products expressed;

c) increase in grain consumption only, showing the decreased levels for the rest of all the animal and plant products.

3.3. Production/consumption and value equilibriums for the resources/consumption balance in the food system

Another aspect of studying the food production and consumption approached by economists is imposed by the knowledge of a three-dimensional assembly characterized by: medium levels and correlative variations; report production / consumption; revenues, earnings and consumers spending. Framed in the analysis structure of main products it was amplified by a deepening of the study focused on adequate statistical indicators, that can capture the implications and why not the real effect of production ↔ consumption interactions in the food market system. Nationally and based on the indicators system production/consumption previously discussed for the 2008-2014 period are given below variational and correlative knowledge levels that characterize the production and consumption in Romania.

Synthetic indicators were analyzed by variations levels, rhythms and annual report production and consumption correlation to the main food products. The data shown in physical units and percentage are shown in Table 6 where it can be deduced the following:

- The average and standard deviation of average estimate the uniformity value of average which records the highest values at cereals and eggs (these amplitudes representing a lower level of consumption of 4.3 times and respectively 25.5 times towards production), so that the output it is more dispersed towards consumption. For other products such deviations production / consumption levels have narrow ranges, so the data set values are clustered around the average;

Table 6. Middle levels and standard deviation variations that characterize production and per capita consumption of main food products in Romania

Product	Production per pers/ consumption per pers.	Mean (2008- 2114) (kg/pers)	Standard deviation (kg/pers)	Variation coefficient (%)	Annual rate (%)	Correlation report(%)
Cereals/pers.	Production	886	178.1	20.10	5.17	0.58
	Consumption	206	6.3	3.04	0.25	
Vegetables/pers.	Production	191	9.7	5.04	0.44	0.43
	Consumption	177	5.0	2.82	0.64	
Fruits/pers.	Production	66.0	5.3	8.06	0.33	0.19
	Consumption	69.7	6.2	8.95	3.12	
Meat/pers.	Production	66.4	2.2	3.27	0.31	0.52
	Consumption	60.3	3.5	5.79	1.48	
Milk/pers.	Production	256	18.4	7.17	2.05	0.68
	Consumption	243	10.6	4.37	0.70	
Eggs/pers.	Production	317	10.2	3.21	0.35	0.68
	Consumption	12.4	0.5	3.62	1.42	

Source (basic calculation): Romanian Statistical Yearbook 2014, INS [3, 4]

- The coefficient of variation expresses in relative data the standard deviation, finding a variation of the levels between production / consumption. Regarding this variational interpretation can be notified two scenarios: a) for cereals, vegetables and milk consumption values are lower than production; b) for fruit, meat and egg the production is lower than the consumption;
- The correlation report describes the degree of linear association between production /consumption considerate as quantitative variables. There is a very strong positive association for most products (levels being between 0.43 and 0.68), but although very weak for fruits (value of only 0.19).

Thus it can be seen that there is a variability that is differentiated between production / consumption and also a pronounced difference in the structure of the products types. It thus appears that there is a linearity between the two variables of interest (production and consumption), which is why the correlation graphs production / consumption were made for the analyzed products for the period 2008-2012. Shown in fig. 1 (grains), fig. 2 (vegetables), fig. 3 (fruit), fig. 4 (meat), fig. 5 (milk) and fig. 6 (eggs), results suggestive that there is a direct link of a polynomial form $y = ax^2 + bx + c$, between production and consumption.

Fig. no. 1. Correlation between production and consumption of grain per capita in 2008-2014

Fig. no. 2. Correlation between production and consumption of vegetables per capita in 2008-2014

Fig. no. 3. Correlation between production and consumption of fruits vegetables per capita in 2008-2014

Fig. no. 4. Correlation between production and consumption of meat per capita in 2008-2014

Fig. no. 5. Correlation between production and consumption of milk per capita in 2008-2014

Fig. no. 6. Correlation between production and consumption of eggs per capita in 2008-2014

Through the polynomial regression model parameters is confirmed the correlative form of each product. The report of determination confirms that production is considered a significant factor influencing variation in different proportions for the consumption of each product.

The actual production/consumption ratio in the period 2008-2014 in Romania is analyzed further and by annual variations of this report but also to comparisons to the year 2008. In table 7 are presented these rates which show the following:

Table 7. Evolution of consumption / production the main food products in Romania

Specification	MU	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
The consumption of grain/production of cereals	%	24.90	27.50	24.18	19.86	32.61	20.90	18.68
	% 2008	100.00	110.44	97.11	79.74	130.98	83.92	75.03
The consumption of vegetables/production of vegetables	%	94.62	87.79	91.40	87.31	100.68	91.17	95.76
	% 2008	100.00	92.77	96.60	92.27	106.40	96.35	101.20
The consumption of fruit/fruit production	%	100.00	95.85	90.30	95.92	126.29	113.21	122.63
	% 2008	100.00	95.85	90.30	95.92	126.29	113.21	122.63
The consumption of meat/meat production	%	102.62	87.99	93.02	83.09	88.40	88.46	92.13
	% 2008	100.00	85.75	90.65	80.97	86.15	86.20	89.78
The consumption of milk/production of milk	%	91.30	86.78	95.06	94.37	100.04	100.29	99.09
	% 2008	100.00	95.05	104.12	103.36	109.58	109.85	108.54
The consumption of eggs/production of eggs	%	4.11	4.00	3.92	3.98	3.86	3.88	3.69
	% 2008	100.00	97.31	95.41	96.85	93.81	94.27	89.86

The source (the basis of calculation): Statistical Yearbook of Romania, 2014, INS [3, 4]

- The existence of some products in which the report consumption/ production had registered very high levels (for year 2008 these rates are between 91.30% and 102.62%), resulting that these consumptions (for the products vegetables, fruit, meat and milk) take most of the production and the trend in the annual rate analyzed is growing ;

- A very low level for the consumption / production report is noted for other categories of products, namely for year 2008 at cereals (24.90%) and eggs (4.11%), the trend in the annual dynamics of the period analyzed is decreasing.

From here, as regards the report on consumption/ production results at national level on the one hand an annual variation, but also differentiated trends on the types of products. Respectively the manifestation of an excessive deficit in order to ensure the food consumption at the national level for vegetables, fruit, meat and milk and which is worse still (which it emerges from the dynamics of the years); the manifestation of a surplus in ensuring the food consumption at the national level for cereals and eggs, to which this level of consumption is reduced (arising from the dynamics of the years).

In regard to this study that includes all those to which food consumption has a specific mobility, of a socio-economic level, it is a matter of knowledge of the revenue and expenditure of the households. This is because the income and expenditure influence the food consumption, and in this case the variations in the rate of the annual levels. It is presented below on the one hand this structure of income, earnings and total expenditure of households, and on the other hand the structure of the total expenditure of households' consumption. From the data presented in value and percentage units in table 8 frames the deduction of a comparative form of the presented indicators, which analyzed in the dynamics of the period 2008-2014 shows the following:

- the total revenues and earnings has a trend growth, given that the comparisons made with the year 2008 these levels amplifies with +17.31 % and +29.64 %;

- from the analysis of the total expenditure recorded annually results a share with an increasing level, this increase having a much higher rhythm than the increase in earnings (compared to the revenues this increase is between + 46.30 % and +51.22 %);

-the consumption total expenditures of households has also an increase but whose annual intensification are lower compared with the other analyzed indicators.

Table no. 8.Income, earnings and the total expenditure (monthly on a household)

Specification	UM	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
The total income of	Lei monthly /household	2,131.67	2,315.99	2,304.28	2,417.26	2,475.04	2,559.05	2,500.7

households	% t 2008	100	108.647	108.09	113.39	116.10	120.049	117.31
Nominal earning average monthly neto	lei/employee	1,309	1,361	1,391	1,444	1,507	1,579	1,697
	% t 2008	100	103.972	106.264	110.31	115.126	120.626	129.64
	% t total income	61.40	58.76	60.36	59.73	60.88	61.70	67.86
The total expenditure of the households	Lei monthly /household	1,915.18	2,047.33	2,062.95	2,183.76	2,244.47	2,317.4	2,269.25
	% t 2008	100	106.9	107.71	114.024	117.194	121.002	118.48
	% t total income	89.84	88.39	89.52	90.34	90.68	90.55	90.74
	% t Nominal earning average monthly	146.30	150.42	148.30	151.22	148.93	146.76	133.72
The total expenditure of consumption of households	lei monthly /household	1,365.36	1,468.6	1,486.43	1,532.29	1,614.06	1,670.04	1,637.46
	% t 2008	100	107.561	108.86	112.226	118.21	122.315	119.92
	% t total income	64.05	63.41	64.50	63.38	65.21	65.26	65.48
	% The total expenditure of the households	71.29	71.73	72.05	70.16	71.91	72.06	72.15
	% t The total income of households	104.30	107.90	106.86	106.11	107.10	105.76	96.49

The source (the basis of calculation): Statistical Yearbook of Romania, 2014, INS [3, 4]

From the analysis on matters which concern the production /consumption report in conjunction with the population incomes/ expenditures, on the background of the annual differences, it appears on the one hand in the comparison consumption/ production of the structure of the products analyzed deficient and surplus forms but also concomitant intensification of both annual rates of increase of revenue and expenditure. The lowest annual growth rate is represented by the increase in the total consumption expenditures, in this case it is necessary the identification of other factors considered significant for food consumption.

Conclusions

From the study concerning the interaction between agricultural production ↔ food consumption nationwide for the period 2008-2014, we can conclude the following:

Conclusion (1). In Romania for the period under review, differentiated levels are manifested in annual agricultural production, the trends being oscillators. Regarding the expressing systems for human consumption it can be seen a variation in annual level, mentioning the increasing trends of consumption/person (for vegetal products) and decreases (for animal products). Differences are represented in the structure of expressions through product/capita, calories/capita, proteins/capita.

Conclusion (2). Regarding the relationship of interference between production and consumption may notice a very strong and positive association with the majority of products, concomitant with the existence of variability between the levels of consumption/production report. In the structure of products have been reported two cases: cereals, vegetables and milk where the consumption values are lower than the production; fruit, meat and egg situation where production is lower than consumption.

Conclusion (3). The level expressed by linear regression model parameters is confirmed for each product correlative forms between the two variables of interest (production and consumption). Correlation report confirms that the production is considered a significant factor that influence the variation in different proportions the consumption for each product (for the period 2008-2014 have been carried out concerning the correlation graphics production/consumption confirming the direct and linear form link).

Conclusion (4). Income/expenditures of population, on the background of the existing differences in the dynamics of the analyzed period, falling under the annual rhythms of the specific indicators through the existence of surplus and also deficit situations (at the same time there is the increase of both the annual growth rates of revenues and expenditure). The lowest annual rate of growth is of total expenditure for consumption, which is why it requires an identification of others indicators considered relevant for the forms of manifestation of food consumption.

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RESEARCH REGARDING MICROBIOLOGICAL CONTAMINATION FOR SOME FOOD PACKING USE

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Abstract. *Packaging constitutes an important source of contamination through contact, so the raw material in the first phase of the technological process and the finished product. The microorganisms that may be present on the surface of the packaging can be grouped into two categories: saprophytic microorganisms and pathogenic microorganisms.*

Between 1.01. 2014 - 31.12.2015 we examined 189 sample packages. The samples were examined following exams: Total number of germs detection (EN ISO 4833), coliform bacteria (ISO 4831 and 4832), and yeasts and molds (ISO 21527-1). The results show that packaging can be a source of microbiological contamination for the food.

Keywords: contamination, expertise, microorganisms, packaging for food.

1. Introduction

The main regulations of the European Commission on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food are: EC Regulation no. 1935/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 2004; EC Regulation no. 2023/2006 of 22 December 2006; EC Regulation no. 450/2009 of 29 May 2009; EC Regulation no. 10/2011 of 14 January 2011; [10,11,12,13]

Packages are subject to these regulations: active and intelligent materials and articles; adhesives; ceramics; cork; rubber; glass; ion exchange resins; metals and alloys; paper and cardboard; plastic materials; printing inks; regenerated cellulose; silicon; textile; paints and coatings products; wax; wood.

The provisions shall not apply to materials and articles which are supplied as antiques; covering or coating materials, such as the materials covering cheese rinds, prepared meat products or fruits, which form part of food and may be consumed together with this; fixed public or private water supply.

Any material or article intended to come into contact directly or indirectly with food must be sufficiently inert to prevent the transfer of constituents to food in quantities large enough to endanger human health or cause an unacceptable change in food composition or alteration of its organoleptic properties.

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Through intelligent materials and means materials and articles which monitor the condition of packaged food or the environment surrounding the food and by active materials and articles, materials and articles that are intended to extend shelf-life or to maintain or improve the condition of packaged food; they are designed to deliberately incorporate components that would release substances into the packaged food or the environment surrounding the food or absorb substances from the packaged food or the environment surrounding the food.

Packaging constitutes an important source of contamination through contact, so the raw material in the first phase of the technological process and the finished product. The microorganisms that may be present on the surface of the packaging can be grouped into two categories: saprophytic microorganisms (Pseudomonas, Micrococcus, Proteus, Streptococcus, Escherichia, Mucor, Rhizopus, etc.) and pathogenic microorganisms (Salmonella, enteropathogenic Escherichia coli, Staphylococcus aureus, Yersinia enterocolitica Campylobacter jejuni, Clostridium perfringens, Clostridium botulinum, Listeria monocytogenes). Packages are contaminated with Salmonella most often and Clostridium perfringens. [1,3,4]

The evolution of microorganisms that may be present on the surface of the packaging depends on the factors such as the intrinsic structure of the package, and the pH of the composition; Extrinsic factors armed with atmospheric relative humidity and temperature of storage space.

Consequences multiplication of microorganisms on the surface of the packaging may be economic - alteration and health - causing poisoning. Natural casings (Pickled) have a high microbial load as they came into contact with the intestinal microbiota (coliform and other bacteria from rotting). From the microbiological point of view artificial membranes typically have a low load but can sometimes help with uploading product spoilage microorganisms. [3]

The National Program of Strategy stipulates that supervision by laboratory testing during the production of other products that come into contact with animal products is a biannual through microbiological examinations, which are: Detection of Total plate count, coliforms and yeasts and molds. [5,6,7,8,9]

2. Materials and methods

Between 1.01. 2014 - 31.12.2015 in Brasov Sanitary Veterinary and Food Safety Laboratory we examined 189 samples packages, as follows: (Table. 1 and Chart no. 1)

Table no. 1
The number of samples

Nr. Crt.	Unit	Type of samples	Number of samples	%	
1.	A	Cutisin for packaging various types of salami, baloney and drums	36	19.05	
	B	Cutisin for packaging various types of salami, baloney and drums	21	11.12	
2.	C	Packing bags for poultry carcasse	43	22.75	
		Transparent sheet	39	20.63	
		Casseroles	Polystyrene	28	14.81
			Plastic	22	11.64
	Total		189	100	

Chart no. 1

The number of samples

Samples were taken from 3 processing units in the county of Brasov, which is composed of cutisin with different uses (packaging some types of salami, baloney and drums), packing bags poultry carcasses, transparency and containers of polystyrene and plastic .

Sampling is governed by Order no. 13 of 24 January 2005 of National Sanitary Veterinary and Food Safety Authority, which regulates the sampling of animal products, products containing raw materials of animal origin ingredients contained in animal products or materials that come into contact with them in order laboratory examination.

Sampling for sending to the laboratory was performed under aseptic conditions. For packaging and sealing of the samples were used for polyethylene for food packaging, the first-time use. These packaged, labeled and sealed were sent to the laboratory within 24 hours.

If artificial membranes for microbiological examination were collected by survey totaling a minimum of 2 m linear portions. (Picture no. 1, 2, 3, 4)

Photo. no. 1 and 2 Cutisin - Polyamide Cooper

Foto No. 3 and 4 Transparent sheet

For microbiological control of others packages were collected by sampling a minimum of 5 and a maximum of 10 containers, so that their total capacity to be a minimum of 1 liter. (Photo no. 5, 6, 7, 8)

Photo. 5 and 6. Plastic bags for packing poultry carcasses

Photo. 7. Polystyrene Casserol

Foto nr. 8. Plastic Casserol

In the case of sampling with a view to their microbiological examination were used sterile saline or sterile distilled water. The washing liquid aseptically prepared in advance was inserted aseptically into the vessel to be controlled. The amount of the washing liquid was equal to 1/100 of the capacity of the vessel to control, and 1 ml of the washing liquid was 100 ml of capacity of the container.

Containers (ex. Trays of plastic and polystyrene) were covered with foil sterilized, and plastic bags for packaging of poultry carcasses, introduced washing liquid, then stirred well by movements in different directions, so that liquid to pass through the same place at least 10 times. It was later collected aseptically washing liquid, which resulted in ships and was immediately inserted in it.

The samples were conducted following exams: Total germ detection (EN ISO 4833), coliform bacteria (ISO 4831 and 4832), and yeasts and molds (ISO 21527-1).

Total Number of Germs determination

The method consist in determining the organotrofe aerobic bacteria mesophilic and is based on the fact that microbial cells present in the sample in contact with the culture medium (Plate Quantum Agar - PCA), will form each of visible colonies after incubation at 30oC for 72 hours.

Seeding was carried out by incorporating and mixing gently in growth medium inoculum of a known amount of the sample in the case of the rinsing liquid or by the deposit directly on the surface of solid culture medium wrapping portions (about 1 cm²). (Photo no. 9 and 10)

Photo no. 9 Sampling taking

Photo no. 9 Deposition on the surface of the culture medium

Glassware was sterilized employed in oven at 180° C for 30 minutes, and the medium sterilized at 121°C for 30 minutes.

Petri plates were incubated at 30° C for 72 hours and after the period of incubation colonies were counted in each box. (Photo no. 11, 12)

Photo no. 11. Introducing plates to incubator

Photo no. 12. Counting of colonies

Determining the number of coliforms

Sowing of three tubes enrichment medium selective double-concentrated liquid (broth lauryl sulphate and sodium tube Durham) with a quantity of sample for testing if the product examined is liquid and a quantity of sample where portions of unit dose. (Photo no. 13 and 14)

Photo no. 13. Tubes with enrichment medium Photo no. 14. Seeding sample

Incubating the tubes with double concentrated medium for 24 hours and concentrated tubes with medium alone for 24 or 48 hours at a temperature of 35°C or 37°C.

Seeding with a loop coil of one tube with the tube set confirmation medium Durham tubes fermentation in which the product gas evolution. Incubate at 35°C and 37°C for 24-48 hours. (Photo no. 15 and 16)

Photo no. 15 Tubes with Durham Tubes Photo no. 16. Fermentation with gas production

Based on the number of tubes showing gas evolution, is to determine the probable number of coliform bacteria per ml or per gram of sample.

Determination of yeasts and molds

Diagnostic procedure establish the count of viable yeasts and molds by colony count technique at 25°C. Yeasts and molds are microorganisms that form colonies at 25°C on selective medium specific.

The methodology of diagnosis was performed in accordance with ISO SR 21527/1 or 2. The culture medium used was agar DG 18 and the dilution solution we used distilled or deionized water. Sowing was done as with NTG. (Photo no. 17 and 18)

Photo no. 17. Seeding sample

Photo no. 18. Moldsi

3. Results and discussion

After analyzing samples from the 3 units provenance we obtained the following results (Table no. 2 and Chart no. 2)

Table no. 2

The number of examined samples and the results obtained

Nr. Crt.	Unit	Type of samples	TNG					
			Number of samples	Obtained results				
				Compliance		Non-compliance		
				No.	%	No.	%	
1.	A	Cutisin for packaging various types of salami, baloney and drums	36	30	83.34	6	16.66	
2.	B	Cutisin for packaging various types of salami, baloney and drums	21	18	85.71	3	14.29	
3.	C	Packing bags for poultry carcasse	43	36	83.72	7	16.28	
		Transparent sheet	39	37	97.87	2	2.13	
		Casseroles	Polystyrene	28	23	82.14	5	17.86
			Plastic	22	19	86.36	3	13.64
	Total			163	86.52	26	13.48	

Chart no. 2

The number of examined samples and the results obtained

Most noncompliance occurred at Unit A (16.66%), then descending at Unit B (14.29%) and Unit C (12.9%).

Of the total samples analyzed it was found that 13.48% were non-compliant, the percentages ranging from 2.13 to 17.86% in the transparency or polystyrene trays for the same Unut - Unit C.

After analyzing samples for determining coliforms, taken from the 3 units of origin following results were obtained: (according to Table no. 3 and Chart no. 3)

Table no. 3

The number of examined samples and the results obtained

Curr. No.	Unit	Type of samples	Coliforms					
			Number of samples	Obtained results				
				Compliance		Non-compliance		
				No.	%	No.	%	
1.	A	Cutisin for packaging various types of salami, baloney and drums	36	32	88.89	4	11.11	
2.	B	Cutisin for packaging various types of salami, baloney and drums	21	19	90.48	2	9.52	
3.	C	Packing bags for poultry carcasse	43	38	88.37	5	11.63	
		Transparent sheet	39	37	94.87	2	5.13	
		Casseroles	Polystyrene	28	25	89.28	3	10.72
			Plastic	22	19	86.36	3	13.64
	Total		189	170	89.71	19	10.29	

Chart no. 3

The number of examined samples and the results obtained

Most noncompliance occurred at Unit A (11.11%), then descending Unit C (9.85%) and Unit B (9.52%).

Of the total samples analyzed it was found that 10.29% were non-compliant, the percentages ranging from 5.13 to 13.64% in the transparency or plastic trays for the same Unit - Unit C. After analyzing samples of the 3 units provenance yielded the following results: (see Table no. 4 and Chart no. 4)

Table no. 4

The number of examined samples and the results obtained

Curr. No.	Unit	Type of samples	Coliforms					
			Number of samples	Obtained results				
				Compliance		Non-compliance		
				No.	%	No.	%	
1.	A	Cutisin for packaging various types of salami, baloney and drums	36	29	80.56	7	19.44	
2.	B	Cutisin for packaging various types of salami, baloney and drums	21	15	71.43	6	28.57	
3.	C	Packing bags for poultry carcasse	43	35	81.40	8	18.60	
		Transparent sheet	39	36	92.31	3	7.69	
		Casseroles	Polystyrene	28	26	92.86	2	7.14
			Plastic	22	18	81.82	4	18.18
	Total		189	159	83.40	30	16.60	

Chart no. 4

The number of examined samples and the results obtained

Most noncompliance occurred at Unit B (28.57%), then descending Unit A (19.44%) and Unit C (12.88%).

Of the total samples analyzed was found that 16.60% were non-compliant, the percentages ranging from 7.14 to 28.57% in polystyrene trays for Unit C, respectively cutisin for packaging various types of salami, baloney and drums at Unit B.

Results showing higher values than the allowable limits (NTG - 1 / cm² Coliform bacteria - 3 / cm², total number of yeasts and molds - absent) are considered unsatisfactory and can mean: cross-contamination or intersections of phases salubrious those unsanitary within functional circuits (ie. touch with the circuit packaging waste) handling, maintenance and / or improper storage, packaging, etc.

The results were brought to the attention of non-compliant operators, who analyzed the possible causes of the occurrence of nonconformities and corrective established deadlines, penalties and increase the frequency number of samples

Conclusions

[1] In case of TNG, 13.48% from all samples analyzed were non-complied, percentages ranging from 2.13 to 17.86% in the transparency or polystyrene trays;

[2] In case of coliform 10.29% from all samples analyzed were non-complied, percentages ranging from 5.13 to 13.64% in the transparency or plastic containers;

[3] In case of yeasts and molds 16.60% from all samples analyzed were non-complied, percentages ranging from 7.14 to 28.57% in polystyrene trays;

[4] The results which indicate higher values than the allowable limits, may signify: intersections of cross contamination or salubrious phases with the unsanitary within functional circuits (ie. Touch with the circuit packaging waste) handling, maintenance and / or improper storage, packaging, etc .;

[5] The packaging can be sources of microbiological contamination of food.

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RESEARCH ON ACTIVE AND PASSIVE MONITORING AEROMICROFLORA IN THE MILK UNITS PROCESSING

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Abstract: *For monitoring aeromicroflora in the milk processing units we have proceeded to sampling procedures for monitoring using active and passive methods that have become an essential tool for environmental monitoring, both in food (workspaces, warehouses, etc.) and in testing laboratories.*

Microbiological examinations were performed: total number of aerobic bacteria detection (TNG) / m³ of air and number of yeasts and molds (Y+M) / m³ air.

We made a passive monitoring using sedimentation method by exposing Petri dishes with culture medium for collecting solid particles settle by gravity. To achieve active monitoring have taken defined amount of air passed through a sampling device directly on a solid culture medium.

After sampling proceeded to incubating the plates at different temperatures, depending on the target organism and then we determined the microbiological load of air through estimating the number of microorganisms expressed as cfu / m³ ,, using calculation formulas and Barzoi Omelianski

In the use of the two methods we concluded that sedimentation method allows an approximate quantitative determination, while the vacuum method allows for accurate quantitative determination

Keywords: microaeroflora, passive and active monitoring, Total Number of Germs - TNG, Yeasts and Mold (Y+M)

Introduction

Microbiological control of air workspaces addresses of processing units, storage, marketing, etc., of foodstuffs for human consumption and premises of testing laboratories.

There are two principal means of monitoring microaeroflorei: passive monitoring and active monitoring. Both are equally important, now becoming an essential tool for environmental monitoring in the food sector.

Depending on how sampling can use two methods - sedimentation and aspiration.

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Sedimentation method is suitable to detect microbial particles which are deposited passively due to the force of gravity. For passive monitoring can use two methods: sedimentation Koch, standard Polish PN 89/Z-04008/08 and sedimentation method as "microbiological methods for laboratory examination of food products of animal origin". [1]

The disadvantages of sedimentation are: the method is non-dimensional (not provide information on the volume of air that collects particles) does not allow a quantitative determination of the exact applicability of the plates is limited, it may monitor only the particulate biologically viable settle out of the air and are deposited on a surface in a given exposure time, can not detect small particles suspended in the air, are influenced by interference and contamination of other sources, agar plates can deteriorate if exposure too long, the pads can become very busy in environments heavily contaminated and data interpretation becomes difficult. [2,6]

Advantages sedimentation are the plates are inexpensive and easy to use, requires no special equipment, use more qualitative analysis microaeroflorei, the data can detect trends and provide an early warning of problems. In an environment with low risk (ex. Food production facilities), the plates can provide a suitable means of microbiological monitoring of air quality.

The method aspiration can be achieved by: impact according to ISO 16000-18 - suitable for cases where expected only low concentrations of microbial, for example. clean rooms, food production facilities, etc; filtration according to ISO 16000-16 - suitable for highly contaminated environments, the technique can cause impaction plate over filling. The method allows the use of decimal dilutions to determine the real number of microorganisms.

It is an active way, by volume (the volume of air provides information from which the particles are collected), and so allow accurate quantitative determination, requiring the use of a device that absorbs a known volume of air.

There are two types of sampling devices commercially available: the slot and the screen. The slot device, air is drawn through a narrow gap, and the particles are deposited on a rotating agar plate. The sieve devices, air is drawn through a perforated plate (sieve) with holes with known diameter and the particles deposited on an agar plate fixed underneath. There is the possibility of grouping several sites with different sizes.

For filtration method, filter membranes obtained after harvesting, are resuspended in 5 ml of saline with 0.01% polysorbate 80 (Tween), this being the initial suspension of the decimal dilutions are prepared. 0.1 ml of these dilutions is dispersed on the surface of the agar plates. [3,4,5]

Whatever the process of harvesting (by impact or by filtration), the number of germs is calculated by reporting the number of colonies developed on the culture medium surface to the volume of air. The calculation for the two methods they were carried out in accordance with ISO 16000-17. [7,8,9,10]

Material and method

The methodology of diagnosis was performed in accordance with EN ISO 4833-1 / 2009 - Horizontal method for the enumeration of microorganisms, Part 1, Colony-count technique at 30° C and SR ISO 21527-2: 2009 Horizontal method for the enumeration of yeasts and molds, part 2, colony-count technique in products with water activity less than or equal to 0.95.

Equipment used to make the diagnosis were: oven, incubator (25 ± 1° C) incubator (30 ± 1° C or 37 ± 1° C) water bath (45 ± 1° C), cabinet protection laminar flow, the colony counting equipment, pH - 0.1 meter accuracy pH unit at 25° C, using a microscope, gas burner, Petri dishes with a diameter of 90-100 mm, disposable unit for the sampling air samples;

For effective monitoring and passive we used Petri dishes standard containing culture media (PCA and DG18), which after opening we have exhibited in spaces controlled by 2 plates with the medium for total plate count by 2 plates with medium yeasts and molds for 10 minutes.

The plates were placed in workrooms at work surfaces in deposits - a plaque on pavement and a board height of 0.8 - 1.0 m, in order to collect sediment particles by their gravitational force. After 10 minutes the plates were covered with lids and were transported immediately to the laboratory.

After incubating the plates at different temperatures, depending on the target organism (NTG or DM), we determined the microbiological charge air by estimating the number of organisms expressed as CFU / m³.

To perform active monitoring have taken a defined amount of air after passing through a sampling device, the particles in the air is collected directly on a solid culture medium using devices sieve, allowing air to be pulled through a plate perforated (sieve) with hole diameter known particles are deposited on an agar plate fixed underneath. After harvesting the plates were identified from the sampling site, packaged, sealed and shipped under refrigeration (2-4°C) to the laboratory, where have been incubated immediately upon arrival.

If yeasts and molds we proceeded to identify yeasts and molds. Their colonies or smear preparations we made and we examined under a microscope with 40 x objective

Results and discussions

Samples were taken from different workspaces two milk processing units in the county of Brasov. The total number of samples collected was 183, of which 114 were obtained by using the sedimentation method, and 69 the suction method.

The 114 samples collected by sedimentation technique, were taken from the following workspaces: (Table. 1 and Chart no. 1)

Table. 1. The number of samples examined by sedimentation method

Nr. Crt.	Name of establishment	Total samples	Space name				
			Raw material reception	Pasteurization	Processing	Packing	Storage
1.	A	71	14	11	16	15	15
2.	B	43	9	-	10	13	11
	Total	114	23	11	26	28	26

Chart no. 1. The number of samples examined by sedimentation method

For taking air sampling we used standard Petri plates containing culture media - TNG PCA and DG18 to Y + M. The culture media were prepared as described and were then cast in Petri dishes having a diameter of 9 cm. Subsequently Petri dishes in number 4 (2 TNG and 2 to Y + M), were positioned in such spaces in table. 1 over an area of 1m² on the floor and other surfaces located at different heights in relation to the (1 - 2m) for 15 minutes.

After this contact, the Petri dishes were covered and immediately transported to the laboratory where they were incubated at 37 ° C in the case of NTG and 25 ° C for the Y + M. The incubation period was 72 hours in TNG and 4-5 days for Y + M after incubation culture media were examined to identify potential colonies developed. (Fig. 1,2,3,4,5,6).

Fig. nr 1. Petri dishes with PCA medium – TNG
(non-compliant samples)

Fig. nr 2. Petri dishes with PCA medium - TNG
(compliant samples)

Fig. nr 3. Petri dishes with PCA medium - TNG
(non-compliant samples)

Fig. nr 4. Petri dishes with PCA medium - TNG
(compliant samples)

Fig. nr. 5. Petri dishes with DG 18 medium - Y + M
(compliant sample)

Fig. nr. 6. Petri dishes with DG 18 medium - Y + M
(non-compliant sample)

Depending on the target organism (TNG or Y+M), we determined the microbiological load by estimating the number of microorganisms air expressed as CFU / m³.

For the calculation we used comparative three formulas: Polish standard PN 89 / Z-04008/08 Omelianski formula and method Barzoi as follows:

1. According to the Polish standard PN 89 / Z-04008/08:

$$\text{CFU/m}^3 \text{ aer} = a \cdot 10.000 / p \cdot t \cdot 0.2$$

where:

a = number of colonies in the Petri dish

p = area in cm^2 Petri plate (for a diameter of 9 cm, $S = 3.14 \times R^2 = 63.5 \text{ cm}^2$)

t = exposure time of the Petri plate

2 According to the formula Omelianski

.....

where:

a = number of colonies in the Petri dish

p = area in cm^2 Petri plate (for a diameter of 9 cm, $S = 3.14 \times R^2 = 63.5 \text{ cm}^2$)

$$\text{CFU/m}^3 \text{ aer} = N \times 10.000 / S \times K$$

where:

N = the number of colonies in the Petri dish

S = surface area in cm^2 Petri plate (for a diameter of 9 cm, $S = 3.14 \times R^2 = 63.5 \text{ cm}^2$)

K = coefficient exposure time (factor) (5 minutes = 1, 10 = 2 min, 15 min = 3)

3. According to the method Barzoi

$$\text{CFU} / \text{m}^3 \text{ air} = n \times 50$$

where:

n = the average number of colonies on the two Petri dishes

For this method uses two Petri dishes with a diameter of 10 cm, exposed for 10 minutes

Calcuation method	Formula
Polish standard PN 89/Z-04008/08	$\text{CFU/m}^3 \text{ air} = a \cdot 10.000 / p \cdot t \cdot 0.2$
Omelianski formula	$\text{CFU/m}^3 \text{ air} = N \times 10.000 / S \times K$
Bărzoi method	$\text{CFU/m}^3 \text{ air} = n \times 50$

Taking in considering the number ufc developed on the surface of media culture plates used for sedimentation of micro-organisms and comparing them to the maximum permitted levels set in the procedure National Sanitary Veterinary Authority on sampling we considered inconsistent all samples were above 600 cfu / m^3 in the case TNG and 300 cfu / m^3 for Y + M. For the calculation we used

standard formulas provided in Polish and Omelianski formula (Table no. 2 and chart no. 2 and 3)

Table. 2. Number of samples compliant and non-compliant

Name of establishment	Total samples		Space name																
			Raw material reception			Pasteurization			Processing			Packing			Storage				
	C	N	C		N		C		N		C		N		C		N		
			No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%			
A	71	66	5	8	12	2	14	11	-	-	15	1	6	13	2	13	15	-	-
B	43	41	2	5	8	1	11	-	-	-	10	-	-	12	1	8	11	-	-
Total	114	106	7	6	20	3	13	11	-	-	25	1	4	25	3	11	26	-	-

C = compliant

N = non - compliant

Chart no. 2. Probe compliant and non-compliant - Unit A

Chart no. 3. Probe compliant and non-compliant - Unit B

Regarding on the three formulas accepted and used it is noted that the results are identical for standard formula Polish and Omelianski and differ slightly from the results obtained after applying the formula Barzoi.

Thus, if two petri dishes and placed on the surface of the culture medium from each plate is developed two cfu, yielding an average of 2 colonies, the results achieved by the three formulas are as follows:

Polisch standard	Omelianski formula	Bărzoi method
$2 \times 10.000/63,5 \times 15 \times 0,2 = 105$	$2 \times 10.000/63,5 \times 3 = 105$	$2 \times 50 = 100$

Result that TNG are consistent when the culture medium on the surface of the 2 plates develops an average exceeding 11 cfu (12 cfu results being true).

If Y + M, if we refer to the maximum possible limit of 300 cfu / m³, the results are in line when the surface of the culture medium of the 2 plates develops an average of more than 5 cfu (from 6 cfu results being true) .

Using aspiration method it was collected 70 samples from the same number space of the processing units A and B of milk from which samples were taken and the sedimentation method, as follows: (Table no. 3)

Table 3. The number of samples by aspiration method

Nr. Crt.	Name of establishment	Total samples	Space name				
			Raw material reception	Pasteurization	Processing	Packing	Storage
1.	A	35	8	5	7	7	8
2.	B	35	9	3	6	10	7
	Total	70	17	8	13	17	15

To perform active monitoring we have taken a defined amount of air that is 100 liters (0.1 m³) using a device that allows the collection of airborne particles directly on a culture medium - DG 18 using mesh devices that allow air to be drawn through a perforated plate (sieve) with holes with known diameter and the particles deposited on an agar plate fixed underneath. (Fig. no. 7 and 8)

Fig. no. 7 and 8. Air sample equipment

After harvesting, the plates were identified, packed, sealed and transported to the laboratory where they were incubated immediately after arrival at 37 ° C in the case of TNG and 25 ° C for the Y + M. The incubation period was 72 hours in TNG and 4-5 days for D + M after incubation culture media were examined to identify potential colonies developed. (Fig. No. 9, 10, 11 and 12).

Fig. no.9. Petri dishes with PCA medium (compliant sample)

Fig. no.10. Petri dishes with PCA medium (non-compliant sample)

Fig. no.11. Petri dishes with DG 18 medium (non - compliant sample)

Fig. no.12. Petri dishes with DG 18 (non-compliant sample)

The number of bacteria was calculated by reporting the number of colonies developed on the culture medium surface to the volume of air. The calculation for the two methods set out in ISO 16000-17. "The air inside. Part 17: Detection and enumeration of molds - based method cultivation. "Pct. 7.6.2 - impact method

- for each sample is analyzed in parallel two different volumes of air (ex. 1 m³ and 2 m³), thus requiring four Petri dishes to sample.
- concentration, expressed as CFU / m³ air, is calculated by formula:

$$CI = nufc / VI$$

where:

nufc = total number of colonies on Petri dishes

VI = total sample volume in cubic meters.

Example:

On the DG18 medium, a sample is analyzed for two different air volume of 100 liters and 200 liters. The counts were obtained the following results: Sample volume of 100 liters (0.1 m^3) - shoulder cfu was developed colonies on the plate 21 1:19 colonies in the plate 2 and the sample volume of 200 liters (0.2 m^3) - the number of cfu was 34 in plate no. 3 and 39 in plate no. 4.

$$C_I = n_{\text{ufc}} / V_I = 40/0,2 = 200 = 2,0 \times 10^2$$

$$n_{\text{ufc}} = 21+19 +34+39 = 113$$

$$V_I = 0,1+0,1+0,2+0,2 = 0,6$$

$$C_I = n_{\text{ufc}} / V_I = 113/0,6 = 188 = 1,9 \times 10^2$$

Taking in consideration the number ufc developed on the surface of media culture plates used for active monitoring and comparing them to the maximum permitted levels set in the procedure of National Sanitary Veterinary and Food Safety Authority on sampling we considered inconsistent all samples were above $600 \text{ cfu} / \text{m}^3$ in the case NTG and $300 \text{ cfu} / \text{m}^3$ for Y + M. (Table. 4)

Table 2. Number of samples compliant and non-compliant

Name of establishment	Total samples		Space name																
			Raw material reception			Pasteurization			Processing			Packing			Storage				
	C	N	C	N	C	N	C	N	C	N	C	N	C	N	C	N			
																	No	%	No
A	71	66	5	8	12	2	14	11	-	-	15	1	6	13	2	13	15	-	-
B	43	41	2	5	8	1	11	-	-	-	10	-	-	12	1	8	11	-	-
Total	114	106	7	6	20	3	13	11	-	-	25	1	4	25	3	11	26	-	-

Chart no. 4. compliant and non-compliant samples - Unit A

Chart no. 4. compliant and non-compliant samples - Unit B

Comparing the number of cfu that develops on the surface of media on air samples by sedimentation method and the air sample taken through active monitoring that when TNG value 12 cfu / m³ corresponds to a total of 360 cfu / m³ which develops on the surface of the culture medium of the four petri dishes and in the case of D + M, a value of 6 cfu / m³ corresponds to an average of 180 cfu / m³ which develops on the surface of the culture medium of 2 Petri dishes. Values greater than these, representing noncompliance, while the volume of the sample taken from monitoring active is 100 liters and 200 liters (0.1 m³ and 0.1 m³)

For this reason, we believe that if the formula for calculating sedimentation, should be amended, taking as a basis for calculating the maximum permissible correspondence value cfu of passive monitoring to active monitoring of the maximum permissible value.

In case of TNG:

$$\text{CFU/m}^3 \text{ aer} = 12 \times 50 = 600$$

$$C_1 = n_{\text{ufc}} / V_1 = 360/0,6 = 600$$

In case of Y+M

$$\text{CFU/m}^3 \text{ aer} = 6 \times 50 = 300$$

$$C_1 = n_{\text{ufc}} / V_1 = 180/0,6 = 300$$

Thus we intend to apply the following formula, which allows for the passive monitoring results more similar to active monitoring. Practical we apply Barzoi method a correction factor, 1.67, so if TNG as such and Y + M, which is the result of dividing the maximum allowable maximum number of cfu may develop on the surface of the four culture media that was They've taken defined amount of air, above which the sample is classed as non-compliant.

$$\text{UFC/m}^3 \text{ aer} = n \times V_{mp}/12 \times V_{ma}/360$$

where:

n = the average colonies developed on the culture medium inside surface of the second

Petri plates (cfu)

V_{ms} = maximum allowable passive monitoring (cfu)

V_{ms} = maximum allowable amount of active monitoring (cfu)

Example:

On the environment have been developed ATP 6 and 8 cfu, so an average of 7 cfu. What is the microbiological load of 1m³ air.

1. Method Bărzoi

$$\text{UFC/m}^3 \text{ aer} = 7 \times 50 = 350$$

2. The calculation method proposed by us

$$\text{CFU/m}^3 \text{ aer} = 7 \times 600/12 \times 600/360 = 7 \times 50 \times 1,67=584,5$$

It follows that the following formula proposed by us, a result inconsistent is when the surface of media number ufc is > 7 in the case of TNG and > 3 when Y + M, unlike the Barzoi method which is bringing non-compliant results when ufc number is > 12 in the case of TNG and > 6 if Y + M

Conclusions

(1) Monitoring passive identified a number of 6% non-compliant samples, while active monitoring 13% of the samples, while the air samples were collected from the same units and workspaces;

(2) Both methods detected microbiological air cargo highest in the same premises and reception areas namely raw material, 13% non-compliant samples for passive monitoring and 18% of the samples for active monitoring. And the other areas there is a correlation approximate, always with the predominance of non-compliant samples for air sampling defined in quantitative terms;

(3) The results obtained from the calculation formula proposed by us allows the number of non-compliant samples to be higher by about 50% in both quasi parameters (NTG and D + M) and thus closer to the number of samples non-compliant results from monitoring active. So after applying the calculation formulas known non-compliant samples ratio is 13: 6 know what the application zrna proposed new formula for calculating the ratio is 13: 12.

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